

Advances in the Therapeutic Delivery and Applications of Functionalized Pluronics: A Critical Review

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Abstract:

Pluronic (PEO-PPO-PEO) block copolymers can form nano-sized micelles with a structure composed of a hydrophobic PPO core and hydrophilic PEO shell layer. Pluronics are U.S. Food and Drug Administration approved polymers, which are widely used for solubilization of drugs and their delivery, gene/therapeutic delivery, diagnostics, and tissue engineering applications due to their non-ionic properties, non-toxicity, micelle forming ability, excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability. Although Pluronics have been employed as drug carrier systems for several decades, numerous issues such as rapid dissolution, shorter residence time in biological media, fast clearance and weak mechanical strength have hindered their efficacy. Pluronics have been functionalized with pH-sensitive, biological-responsive moieties, antibodies, aptamers, folic acid, drugs, different nanoparticles, and photo/thermo-responsive hydrogels. These functionalization strategies enable Pluronics to act as stimuli responsive and targeted drug delivery vehicles. Moreover, Pluronics have emerged in nano-emulsion formulations and have been utilized to improve the properties of cubosomes, dendrimers and nano-sheets, including their biocompatibility and aqueous solubility. Functionalization of Pluronics results in the significant improvement of target specificity, loading capacity, biocompatibility of nanoparticles and stimuli responsive hydrogels for the promising delivery of a range of drugs. Therefore, this review presents an overview of all advancements (from the last 15 years) in functionalized Pluronics, providing a valuable tool for industry and academia in order to optimize their use in drug or therapeutic delivery, in addition to several other biomedical applications.

Keywords: Functionalized Pluronics, Drug delivery, Theranostics, Hydrogels, Nanoparticles, Nanosheets, Aptamers, Antibody

Abbreviations:

¹H-NMR, ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance; DHP-bMPPA, 2,2'-bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid; 5-FU, 5-fluorouracil; AA, Acrylic acid; AIE, Aggregation-induced emission; AAS, Atomic absorption spectroscopy; BA, Betulinic acid; BBB, Blood brain barrier; BOSA, (9, 10-bis(4-butoxystyryl) anthracene) donor; BCRPs, Breast cancer resistant proteins; BRT, Brimonidine tartrate; CO₂, Carbon dioxide; CMCS, Carboxymethyl chitosan; CA, Carboxymethyl hexanoyl chitosan; CvME, Caveolae-mediated endocytosis; CET, Cetuximab; Ce6, Chlorin e6; CQ, Chloroquine; CIS, Cisplatin; CME, Clathrin-mediated endocytosis; *cmc*, Critical micelle concentration; *cmt*, Critical micelle temperature; cryo-TEM, cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy; CUR, Curcumin; CD, Cyclodextrin; Cy, Cypate; CYS, Cystamine; CoQ10, Coenzyme Q10; DSC, Differential scanning calorimetry; DTX, Docetaxel; DOX, Doxorubicin; DLS, Dynamic Light Scattering; EGFR, Epidermal growth factor receptor; bFGF, Fibroblast growth factor; FR, Folate receptor; FA, Folic acid; FTIR, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; GA, Glutaraldehyde; GSH, Glutathione; GNPA, Gold nanoaggregates; GNPs, Gold nanoparticles; HON, Honokiol; HA, Hyaluronic acid; HLB, Hydrophilic-lipophilic balance; HPMC, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose cellulose; IBU, Ibuprofen; IFX, Infliximab; CPT-11, Irinotecan; CLSM, Laser confocal scanning microscopy; LA, Linoleic acid; LPEI, Low molecular weight polyethyleneimine; LCST, Lower critical solution temperature, MSNs, Mesoporous silica nanoparticles; MTX, Methotrexate, MB, Methylene blue; MDR, Multidrug resistance; MRPs, Multiple resistant proteins; TMC, N,N,N-trimethyl chitosan; NCs, Nanocapsules; NPs, Nanoparticles; Nap, Naproxen; NP, Nepafenac; NCS, Niclosamide; NR, Nile red; NO, Nitric oxide; OA, Osteoarthritis; PTX, Paclitaxel; PBS, Phosphate Buffer Saline; P-gp, P-glycoprotein; PLGA, Poly lactic-co-glycolic acid; PLA, Poly(lactic acid); PAMAM, Poly-amidoamine; PEG, Polyethylene glycol; PEO, Polyethylene oxide; PEI, Polyethyleneimine; PPO, Polypropylene oxide; PPI, Polypropyleneimine; PQ, Primaquine; QD, Quantum dots; QCT, Quercetin; ROS, Reactive oxygen species; rhEGF, Recombinant human epidermal growth factor; RES, Resveratrol; RSV, Rosuvastatin; SEM, Scanning electron microscopy; SEDDS, Self-emulsifying drug delivery system; siRNA, Short interfering RNA; SIL, Sildenafil; SLB, Silibinin; SAXS, Small-angle X-ray scattering; NaCMC, Sodium carboxymethylcellulose; SPIONs, Superparamagnetic iron oxide NPs; TEL, Telmisartan; TGA, Thermogravimetric analysis; TF, Tissue factor; TPP, Triphenylphosphonium; TEM, Transmission Electron Microscopy; VER, Verteporfin; XRD, X-ray diffraction; TOC, α -tocopherol; β -TCP, β -tricalcium phosphate

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1.0 Introduction:

Pluronics, also known as Poloxamers, are commercially available ABA-type triblock copolymers, consisting of polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polypropylene oxide (PPO) units arranged in a PEO-PPO-PEO structure [1,2]. They are comprised of a collection of over fifty amphiphilic, water-soluble molecules and the first letter of their name represents their physical state: L, P and F for liquid, paste, and flake, respectively (represented in **Figure 1** as “Pluronic grid” system) [3]. Since the Pluronic polymer chains consist of both hydrophilic PEO and hydrophobic PPO blocks, it enables them to form micelles at or above the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) and critical micelle temperature (*cmt*) [4]. The hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) of the Pluronic copolymers depends upon the length of the blocks. Pluronics gained substantial attention over conventional block copolymers due to their advantageous properties such as high surface-activity, high loading capacity, low-toxicity, low immunogenicity with excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability [5-8].

Pluronic-based nanotechnology is rapidly growing and one of the most attractive fields of pharmaceutical research. The size, adsorption properties and structure of Pluronics make them suitable for use in a broad range of applications such as drug delivery, cosmetics, emulsion formulations and nanoparticles (NPs) synthesis [9-11]. Numerous publications have demonstrated that Pluronics can act as drug delivery vehicles due to their intrinsic ability to accommodate drugs in both the PPO block formed core and the PEO forming corona region, as well as preventing degradation of drugs in biological media. Additionally, the hydrophilic region (PEO) extends the circulation time in the body by providing steric stability [12-14]. Pluronics are considered inert carriers for drug delivery but recent reports proved that they can act as a biological response modifier and increase the transport of drugs across the blood brain and intestinal barriers, as well as into tissues and cells. For instance, Pluronics have the capacity to sensitize multidrug resistance (MDR) cancer cells by inhibiting the drug efflux protein, breast

cancer resistant proteins (BCRPs) [15], multiple resistant proteins (MRPs) [16] and changing the micro-viscosity by incorporating into the membrane [17]. However, Pluronics possess several drawbacks including short residence time in complex biological media and fast dissolution of micelles, resulting in premature release of drug-load [18.19].

Pluronic properties can be modified by using different polymers, surfactants and adjuvants. For example, a mixed system of Pluronic F127, hyaluronic acid (HA) and chondroitin sulfate (trade name ZIVEREL®) is in clinical trials for the treatment of esophagitis induced by radiotherapy in cancer patients [20]. Mediclore, an anti-adhesive hydrogel formulation consisting of Pluronic and chitosan, is already on the market [21]. Furthermore, the efficacy and safety of a mixed solid of Pluronic, gelatin and chitosan (known as Mediclore®) as an anti-adhesive barrier is in clinical trial for intraperitoneal [22] and intrauterine surgery in patients with gynaecological diseases and for post axillary dissection for breast cancer [23]. Thus, these ongoing clinical trials and marketed formulations evidence that Pluronics have drug delivery applications as commercial point of view.

However, the target specific delivery, stability and rapid metabolism of certain drugs, in addition to their excretion without achieving required effects are major concerns as they hinder their use as an effective drug delivery vehicle [24]. Extensive research has focused on overcoming these disadvantages and Pluronics are being modified with different moieties to make them stimuli responsive [25] The functionalization of Pluronics with redox sensitive linkers, folic acid (FA) and specific drugs has been performed for target specific delivery. Moreover, to increase their physical stability, they are conjugated with dendrimers and cubosomes. NPs-functionalized Pluronics (primarily gold, magnetic and silica) have also been used for this purpose. Similarly, Pluronic-based hydrogel systems including chitosan, photo-responsive and HA cross-linked hydrogels are now used mainly for local and transdermal delivery. The primary objective of this review is to discuss the recent developments in Pluronic

functionalization for their therapeutics delivery and biomedical applications. To the best of our knowledge, this article covers all aspects of the functionalization of Pluronic, which have not been reviewed to date.

Figure 1: Pluronic PEO-PPO-PEO copolymers arranged in the "Pluronic grid". The copolymers along the vertical lines have the same PPO/PEO composition ratio, while the copolymers along the horizontal lines have PPO blocks of the same length.

2.0 Functionalized Pluronic- Functionalization of Pluronic with redox sensitive moieties [26-36], FA for targeting specific cells [37-55], dendrimers [56-74], cubosomes [75-94], drugs [95-114], polysaccharides [115-124] and biotin (BIO) [125-131] are straightforward methods to modify the property of native Pluronic to develop target responsive systems. In this section, we will discuss these different methods of Pluronic modification:

2.1 Redox sensitive (Glutathione (GSH)-Enzyme responsive) Pluronic micelles-

Redox-sensitive polymeric micelles and conjugates have emerged as a promising class of smart biomedical materials that can be applied for the development of sophisticated drug delivery systems. These micelles generally have characteristic disulfide linkages, which are prone to rapid cleavage through thiol-disulfide exchanges under a reductive environment at a time scale varying from minutes to hours [26]. Polymers with disulphide linkage can be designed to achieve rapid drug release in cancer cells, which is triggered by the higher intracellular concentration of GSH [27,28]. For example, Liu and co-worker synthesized a redox-sensitive Pluronic F127-SS- α -tocopherol (TOC) polymer using a disulphide bond to link F127 and TOC, which leaves in response to a reductive environment of intracellular GSH in cancer cells [29]. A two-step esterification reaction was carried out to synthesize a TOC modified F127 polymer (F127-SS-TOC). F127-SS-TOC formed stable micelles at relatively low critical micelle concentration and was sensitive to the intracellular redox environment. F127-SS-TOC micelles at concentrations ranging from 12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ exhibited low cytotoxicity on both L02 (liver cell line) and Bel 7402 liver cancer cells. This report exemplified that disulphide linkage in Pluronic micelles have a considerable potential for drug delivery and other drugs can be also be conjugated in a similar way to achieve Pluronic-based redox sensitive drug delivery. In line with the previous study, the same research group loaded the natural polyphenolic anticancer drug resveratrol (RES) in redox-sensitive polymeric micelles (Pluronic F127 (F127)-SS-TOC) [30]. RES loaded F127-SS-TOC micelles showed significantly higher cytotoxicity in human breast cancer cells including MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 compared to free RES and non-redox-sensitive RES loaded F127-TOC micelles. *In vitro* cell line results demonstrated that redox-sensitive RES loaded F127-SS-TOC micelles could induce apoptosis and elevate the intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) level against MDA-MB-231 cells [**Figure 2**]. These results indicated that redox sensitive RES loaded F127-SS-TOC micelles have potential in enhancing the treatment of breast cancer.

Figure 2: Pictorial presentation of bio reducible disulphide bond containing Pluronic F127 micelles (RES-loaded F127-SS-TOC). Reprinted from Ref 35; Liu *et al.*, RSC advances, 2017, 7:47091, Copyright (2017) Royal Society of Chemistry.

Bioreducible doxorubicin (DOX) cross-linked Pluronic micelles for folate-mediated cancer targeting were developed by Nguyen and co-worker [31]. Acrylic acid has been embedded within the hydrophobic block of amine-terminated Pluronic F127 to obtain acrylic acid (AA) conjugated Pluronic (AA-Pluronic-NH₂). Sequentially, FA, hydrazine, and cystamine (CYS) were coupled to AA-Pluronic-NH₂, after that DOX was coupled through an acid-labile hydrazone bond (FA-Pluronic-C/H-DOX). These micelles can specifically target cancer cells through the folate-mediated cancer targeting mechanism and addition of dithiothreitol (a reducing agent) in the releasing media resulted in the rapid DOX release due to the reduction of disulphide bonds. Zhang and colleagues synthesized linoleic acid (LA) disulphide coupled Pluronic F68 (F68-SS-LA) for the intracellular redox sensitive delivery of anticancer drug

brusatol [32]. Hydrophobic nature of LA favours the self-assembly of modified Pluronic F68 (F68-SS-LA) to form flower-like micelles. Cytotoxicity studies performed on the Bel-7402 and MCF-7 cell lines evidenced that F68-SS-LA micelles have greater cellular internalization as compared to the free brusatol and pure F68 micelles. Mixed micelles of betulinic acid (BA)

Figure 3: Cell viability of 4T1 cells toward free BA, blank F68-Cy and P-SS-BA/F68-Cy incubation for 48 h (A) without NIR laser irradiation or (B) with NIR laser irradiation (C) Optical images of 4T1 tumour spheres treated with different samples. Reprinted from Ref 38; Zhang *et al.*, Colloids and Surfaces A, 2021; 609:125662, Copyright (2021), with permission from Elsevier.

conjugated polyethylene glycol (PEG) polymer (P-SS-BA) and Cypate (Cy) grafted with Pluronic were prepared by Zhang and colleagues [33]. The different PEG polymers such as

PEG₂₀₀₀, PEG₅₀₀₀ and PEG₁₀₀₀₀ and different Pluronics (F68, F108 and F127) were explored to achieve the desired drug loading efficiency. The self-assembled mixed micelles exhibited the redox-responsive disulphide bond in BA prodrug and NIR responsive Pluronics.

In vitro drug release studies revealed that at pH 7.4 PBS (Phosphate Buffer Saline) without GSH, moderate release of BA was observed while the presence of 10 mM GSH at pH 5.0 PBS accelerated the BA release. Synergistic chemotherapeutic effect of designed mixed micelles and NIR radiation was evidenced from the *in vitro* cytotoxic studies and *in vivo* anti-tumour activity [Figure 3]. Recently, Vadivelmurugan and co-worker synthesized redox sensitive MoS₂ nanocomposites for the delivery of DOX in cancer therapy [34]. MoS₂ nanocomposites were conjugated with Pluronic F127 by inserting CYS and GSH to obtain MoS₂-GSH-CYS-

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the Steps Involved in the Synthesis of TF targeted-SS-Pluronic F108. Reprinted from Ref 40; Rangasami *et al.*, *Biomacromolecules*, 2021; 22: 1980, Copyright (2021) American Chemical Society.

F127. Upon incubation of the MoS₂-GSH-CYS-F127 nanocomposites in a GSH environment, a change in the morphology of the material was induced which led to drug release. After 2-4 hours of incubation of the DOX loaded nanocomposite, partial release was observed

in cytoplasm of HeLa cells (cervical cancer cell line) while effective release of DOX was obtained into the nucleus after 6 hours. Rangasami *et al.* investigated the delivery of bone marrow derived BMSCs using tissue factor (TF) targeting short interfering RNA (siRNA) conjugated Pluronic F108, schematic of TF targeted-SS-Pluronic F108 is presented in Figure 4 [35]. The feasible delivery of BMSCs was achieved by silencing TF, a transmembrane protein

which initiates procoagulant activity. Consequently, siRNA modified Pluronic F108 diminished the thrombotic activity which increases the survival and functions of BMSCs. Thiol-exchange reaction played the role in the formation of disulphide bonds between the siRNA and pendant pyridyl disulfide modified Pluronic F108 (TF targeted-SS-Pluronic F108). Later, Kadekar and colleagues explored the site-specific delivery of siRNA achieved by disulfide modified Pluronic F108 [36]. In this context, the COOP peptide that targets mammary-derived growth inhibitor receptor was conjugated with Pluronic F108 for the specific delivery of siRNA. Interestingly, this work emphasized that the formulated Pluronic-based thermoresponsive siRNA drug delivery system can be used for intracellular delivery of siRNA.

2.2 Folic acid (FA) conjugated Pluronics

MDR is one of the most pressing dilemmas in cancer therapy. Pluronic block copolymers can be covalently modified with the targeting agent like FA to recognize and bind a variety of tumour cells via their surface-overexpressed folate receptor (FR). The combined mechanisms of Pluronic-mediated P-glycoprotein (P-gp) inhibition and FR-mediated active internalization [Figure 5] could be beneficial in treatment of MDR solid tumours [37,38]. To explore how FA functionalized Pluronics can enhance the internalization of drug molecules to achieve targeted drug delivery [39,40], we will discuss several studies. Wang *et al.* conjugated FA with Pluronic P105/L101 for the delivery of Paclitaxel (PTX) [41]. The conjugation of FA to Pluronic P105/L101 was performed by activation of the terminal hydroxyl group of P105/L101 by 4-nitrophenyl chloroformate and amination of FA by ethylene diamine. In human breast cancer cells MDR sublines, MCF-7/ADR cells, the uptake of folate-conjugated P105/L101 micellar PTX was almost 3 times greater than PTX loaded pure P105/L101 micelles. Moreover, a significant reduction in IC₅₀ of PTX in MDR cells was observed as compared to free PTX. Greater cytotoxicity of Pluronic micellar PTX indicated better susceptibility of MDR cells as

compared to the parental cells. FA tethered Pluronic F127 polymers were synthesized with an esterification reaction [42]. The high-pressure homogenization method was applied to produce NPs using FA conjugated Pluronic F127 and vegetable oil. Pluronic F127-based NPs were more efficiently internalized *in vitro* in cancer cells than PEGylated albumin-based NPs. This was by virtue of the interaction of FA with the cell membrane and Pluronic F127-based NPs having FA exhibited efficient disruption inside the cancer cells. Liu and colleagues encapsulated CdTe/ZnS core/shell quantum dots (QD) in carboxylated Pluronic F127 micelles [43]. Following this, FA was conjugated with carboxylated Pluronic F127 loaded CdTe/ZnS core/shell quantum dots for the targeted delivery to the pancreatic cancer cells by exploiting the overexpressed FA receptors (FARs). Cytotoxicity assay evidenced minimal *in vitro* toxicity of QD formulation. Confocal microscopy on Panc-1 (pancreatic cancer) cells demonstrated the uptake of bioconjugate QDs (FA-Pluronic F127). Furthermore, *in vivo* imaging revealed that

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of Drug loaded FA functionalized Pluronic to Folate receptor (FR) positive cancer cells.

bioconjugated Qds were effective in targeting the tumour in mice. Xu and co-worker reported a FA decorated Pluronic P123-Poly(ethylenimine) (PEI) and Pluronic L121 mixed micelles for the delivery of PTX [44]. Pluronic-PEI copolymers were synthesized with Pluronic P123 and PEI followed by the conjugation of FA to the surface of Pluronic-PEI copolymers. Mixed micelles composed of FA conjugated P123-PEI and L121 demonstrated enhanced uptake by phagocytic cells and a significant change in their *in vivo* biodistribution. Pluronic P123 PEI micelles exhibited higher antitumour activity in HeLa cells as compared to the original micelles with the IC_{50} declining significantly to $0.25 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for P123-PEI micelles. Hussein *et al.* used ultrasound waves as an external stimulus to release DOX from the FA conjugated Pluronic P105 micelles [45]. The results showed that the percentage drug release increased as the power intensity of ultrasound increases. The maximum amount of release (14%) was observed at 5.4 W/cm^2 (watts per centimetre squared) with shock wave of ultrasound intensity (70 kHz). Lu *et al.* synthesized aggregation-induced emission (AIE) fluorophores loaded FA-conjugated-F127 nano-micelles through a modified desolvation method [46]. By encapsulating both BOSA (9, 10-bis(4-butoxystyryl) anthracene) donor and bis(4-(N-(2-naphthyl)phenylamino)-phenyl)fumaronitrile acceptor simultaneously within the NPs (NPs), a significant FRET effect was induced, which contributed to the notable increase of acceptor emission. Proof-of-application of these functionalized NPs was provided by analysis with FR-overexpressed cells, demonstrating specific fluorescent signals for the MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Niu and co-worker synthesized and characterized Pluronic P105-FA and P105-glucose mixed micelles for the dual brain tumour-targeting of drug DOX in C6 glioma cells [47]. The blood brain barrier (BBB) model showed efficient brain targeting by DOX loaded Pluronic P105-FA and P105-glucose mixed micelles which was possibly achieved by the combined effect of mixed micelles; by transportation of glucose transporter and active tumour cell targeting by FR receptor-mediated endocytosis. Xiong *et al.* synthesized a novel FA-Pluronic

F87-poly(lactic acid) (FA-F87-PLA) conjugate [48]. The effective targeting behaviours of FA-F87-PLANPs have been evidenced by *in vitro* cytotoxicity test in OVCAR-3 cells using PTX as a model drug [Figure 6]. Moreover, FA-F87-PLA NPs specifically delivered the PTX drug to FR overexpressed tumour cells. Xiong *et al.* further observed the improved loading capacity

Figure 6: Internalization and localization of FA-F87-PLA NPs in the cytoplasmic compartment of OVCAR-3 cells. Fluorescent images for cells incubated with FA-F87-PLA NPs (a), and subsequently stained with nucleus-selective dye Hoechst 33342 (b) and plasma membrane-selective dye DiO (c), (d) is the corresponding phase-contrast photograph. Reprinted from Ref. 53; Xiong *et al.*, European Polymer Journal, 2015;68:233, Copyright (2015), with permission from Elsevier.

and anticancer efficiency of PTX-loaded FA-F87-PLA micelles [49]. D-tocopheryl-poly(ethyleneglycol)-1000 succinate (TPGS or Vitamin E TPGS) was added into the FA-F87-PLA micelles to form FA-F87-PLA/TPGS mixed micelles. The *in vitro* cytotoxicity of PTX loaded FA-F87-PLA/TPGS and cellular uptake of coumarin6-loaded FA-F87-PLA/TPGS mixed micelles was higher than the pristine PTX loaded FA-F87-PLA and coumarin6-loaded FA-F87-PLA micelles. The decreased particle size and inhibition of P-gp effect induced by the addition of TPGS could result in enhancing the cellular uptake and improving the antitumour efficiency of PTX-loaded FA-F87-PLA/TPGS mixed micelles. To access the delivery of PTX two folate targeted polymeric block copolymers, FA-F127-PLA and FA-P85-PLA have been synthesized [50]. The *in vitro* targeting behaviour of PTX-loaded FA-Pluronic-PLA NPs against OVCAR-3 cells (FR positive) was proved by the cytotoxicity tests. The *in vivo* targeting properties of NPs were also studied in OVCAR-3 ovarian tumour-bearing mice. It was observed that the tumour growth percentage for targeted PTX-loaded FA-F127-PLA NPs was lower than that for non-targeted PTX-loaded PLA-F127-PLA NPs. Consistent with these

studies, Gong *et al.* synthesized FA-Pluronic P85 and F127 conjugates which were used to initiate the ring-opening polymerization of cyclic monomer caprolactone to obtain the final FA-Pluronic-polycaprolactone (FA-Pluronic-PCL) block copolymer [51]. The effect of FA ligand density of FA-Pluronic-PCL micelles on their targeting properties were examined by cytotoxicity and fluorescence methods using an OVCAR-3 (ovarian cancer cells) cell line. The target specific ability of FA-Pluronic-PCL NPs were observed as compared to unconjugated (PCL-Pluronic) micelles. It was observed that FA-F127-PCL NPs with 10% FA molar content had higher effective antitumour activity and cellular uptake than those with 50% and 91% FA molar content. Continuing the research on FA conjugated Pluronic, Xie *et al.* designed novel FA-targeted poly lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA) polymersome (FA-P85-PLGA) for oral delivery of insulin [52]. MTT assay showed that FA-P85-PLGA and PLGA-P85-PLGA polymersomes have good biocompatibility. Fluorescein isothiocyanate labelled insulin (FITC)-loaded FA-P85-PLGA polymersomes exhibited higher cellular uptake than FITC-insulin-loaded PLGA-P85-PLGA polymersomes and free FITC-insulin. Better hypoglycemic effects with FA-P85-PLGA than insulin-loaded PLGA-P85-PLGA proved the effect of the FA receptor-mediated endocytosis for targeted polymersomes. Authors emphasised that these FA-P85-PLGA polymersomes could be used for the oral delivery of other pharmaceutical peptides and proteins. Furthermore, Pawar *et al.* prepared FA conjugated Pluronic F127 micelles to solubilize natural flavonoid Fisetin [53]. FA-conjugated F127 was synthesized by carbodiimide crosslinker chemistry. Bioavailability of Fisetin from FA conjugated Pluronic F127 micelles was increased by 6-fold with long circulation time, slower plasma elimination and no sign of tissue toxicity as compared to free Fisetin. The IC₅₀ concentration of the Fisetin was effectively decreased from 14.3 mg/ml to 9.8 mg/ml while using Fisetin loaded FA-conjugated F127 micellar formulation. Potara and colleagues reported Pluronic-chitosan-FA functionalized polymeric nanocapsules for the photodynamic and photothermal therapy of IR780 NIR dye

[54]. First, IR780 NIR dye were encapsulated in the Pluronic F127 micelles, followed by subsequent loading in chitosan polymers and FA grafting using EDC-NHS chemistry. Specific intracellular delivery of the FA functionalized nanocapsules loaded IR780 NIR dye was confirmed by NIR fluorescence imaging assays and revealed active targeting capacity in FR expressing ovarian cancer cells. FA conjugated Pluronic F127 (F127-FA) nanomicelles were prepared by Ghalekhondabi *et al*, for the solubilization of Silibinin (SLB) for the targeted drug delivery in liver cancer cells [55]. The *in vitro* release evidenced the slow and sustained release behaviour of SLB as compared free SLB. Furthermore, SLB-F127-FA nanomicelles corroborated the higher cytotoxicity in human liver cancer cells as that of non-targeted nanomicelles (SLB-F127) or free SLB, suggesting their potential as drug delivery carriers.

2.3 Dendrimers functionalized Pluronics:

Dendrimers are the class of polymers that are known for their highly branched three-dimensional structures [56]. Dendrimers due to their unique treelike structure [57] are promising materials for use in different biomedical applications ranging from gene and drug delivery [58-60] to magnetic resonance imaging [61]. Despite these wide range of applications, the main hurdle for use of dendrimers in biomedical applications is their cytotoxicity [62]. To overcome these issues, different generations of dendrimers are conjugated with biocompatible polymers such as Pluronics to eliminate their cytotoxic effects to cells. However, the conjugation of dendrimers to Pluronics has resulted in enhanced gene and drug loading capacity as compared to bare Pluronic micelles. Dung *et al*. studied the delivery of antisense oligonucleotides using Poly-amidoamine (PAMAM) dendrimer (generation 5 (G5)) conjugated with Pluronic F127 [63]. MTT assay revealed that dendrimer G5-Pluronic F127 conjugates were non-toxic to gingival fibroblast cells with reduced acute toxicity due to the increased mole ratio of dendrimer to Pluronic. Hao and colleagues investigated Pluronic P123 conjugated third generation cationic dendritic polymeric polypropyleneimine (PPI) system for the gene delivery

[64]. Cytotoxicity of P123-PPI polymeric complexes was noticed to be substantially lower as compared to PPI alone. The NPs can prevent the degradation of plasmid DNA by DNase I. The transfection efficiency was increased significantly upon the addition of free P123 to PPI/DNA NPs in the presence of fetal bovine serum. Wang and colleagues developed a library of PAMAM conjugated F68 polymeric system for the delivery of DOX, which showed enhanced anti-cancer activity in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [65]. The PAMAM-F68 conjugates altered the ROS, MMP and MDR-related genes which led to increased cell apoptosis. The PAMAM-Pluronic F68 conjugates enhanced the cytotoxicity due to the successful delivery of DOX to the nuclei. Deeper penetration was observed in the MCF-7/ADR tumour spheroids for the DOX-loaded PAMAM-F68 complexes than for free DOX. Synthesis of low molecular weight polyethyleneimine (LPEI) conjugated Pluronic was reported by Wang and co-worker [66]. The authors synthesised various dendrimer functionalized Pluronics using Pluronic P123, F68, F127 and F108 (different molecular weights), and combining it with two LPEIs (Mw: 0.8k, 1.2k Da). The promising capability of these LPEI conjugated Pluronics was to adhere and condense plasmid DNA efficaciously into various sub-particles whose size reach up to 200 nm. Higher gene delivery efficacy and less cytotoxicity of LPEI was noted when compared with PEI 25k in C2C12 myoblasts and CHO cells. Nguyen *et al.* have synthesized four different kinds of dendrimer functionalized Pluronics (P123, F68, F127 and F108) and introducing modifications by linking of the G4 PAMAM dendrimer [67]. It has been demonstrated that PAMAM conjugated with Pluronic P123 (G4.0-P123) was found to exhibit higher drug loading efficacy in comparison to lesser lipophilic Pluronics. Drug-loaded nanocarriers have also shown significant antiproliferative activity against MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Emanuele *et al.* have studied the synthesis of conjugated propranolol-G3 PAMAM/lauroyl-G3 dendrimers [68]. The effect on the transport of propranolol, which is a poorly soluble drug and Cyclosporin A (P-gp efflux transporter inhibitor), across monolayers of human colon adenocarcinoma cell

line (Caco-2) have also been studied. The conjugated propranolol dendrimers were prepared in a manner by slowly adding the solution of propranolol-N-chloroacetyl to G3 solutions prepared in anhydrous dimethylformamide. Transport efficiency of propranolol conjugated dendrimers was expressed in terms of apparent permeability coefficient and P-gp inhibitor cyclosporin A imparting that conjugation of drug to dendrimer allows the bypassing of the efflux transporter. Gu *et al.* have employed ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), elemental analysis and the ninhydrin assay for the synthesis and characterization of conjugated Pluronic PF127 attached with PAMAM dendrimers [69]. The prepared PF127-attached PAMAM dendrimer-DOX complex has hydrophobic DOX incorporated in the hydrophobic cavity of F127-attached PAMAM dendrimers. They examined the lower haemolytic and cytotoxicity activity of conjugated PAMAM dendrimers as compared to PAMAM but high drug encapsulation ability. It was found that PAMAM-19% F127 had the ability to retain ~ 12.87 molecules of DOX per conjugate, which was higher compared to PAMAM-57% F127. In another report, the same researchers reported the transfection efficiency, cellular uptake and intracellular mechanisms of DNA loaded Pluronic P123-PPI (P123-PPI/pDNA) based dendrimerosome [70]. The presence of P123 was the main factor influencing the transfection efficiency of P123-PPI/pDNA dendrimerosome in MCF-7/ADR cells and internalization of this dendrimerosome was obtained through the clathrin-mediated endocytosis (CME), caveolae-mediated endocytosis (CvME), and micropinocytosis. Authors conferred that both CME and CvME played an important role in the effective transfection of P123-PPI/pDNA dendrimerosomes. Gao and co-worker have synthesized carbon dioxide (CO_2) responsive new dendritic polymers, comprising of poly(amido amine), PAMAM core and Pluronic F127 chain ends [71]. PAMAM-F127 dendritic polymers were found to self-assemble into unimolecular micelles at low concentration and transformed to multimolecular micelles at higher concentration. Moreover, curcumin (CUR) was loaded in to PAMAM-F127

gels and *in-vitro* drug release behaviour was observed. The results indicated that PAMAM-F127 dendritic polymer can be used to enhance the solubility of CUR, and the presence of CO₂ results in the faster release of drug. Study revealed that CO₂ responsive fluorescent dendritic polymers own promising application in cellular imaging or drug-controlled release. Movellan *et al.* have synthesized various dendrimers derivatives using 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid (bis-MPA) and Pluronic polymers [72]. The aim of their study was to evolve low-cost nanovectors which are susceptible to concentrate drugs and delivering them to Plasmodium-infected cells with advanced specificity and effectivity. Four different types of dendrimers derivative have been tested for their loading capacity for the antimalarial drugs chloroquine (CQ) and primaquine (PQ). Moreover, their specific targeted delivery to Plasmodium-infected red blood cells along with their antimalarial activity *in vitro* against the human pathogen Plasmodium falciparum and *in vivo* against the rodent malaria species Plasmodium yoelii have been investigated. Such findings rendered a new pathway for targeted drug delivery using dendritic derivatives and establish beneficiary in malaria eradication programs. Cros and coworkers have synthesized and characterized two different types of dendritic polymers that can act as vehicles for the transport of antimalarial drugs [73]. These polymers, first, the hybrid-dendritic-linear-dendritic block copolymer based on Pluronic F127 and amino terminated 2,2'-bis(glycyloxymethyl)propionic acid dendrons with a poly(ester amide) skeleton (HDLDBC-bGMPA) and second, amino terminated dendronized hyperbranched polymer with a polyester skeleton derived from 2,2'-bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid (DHP-bMPA) can self-assembled in water to form micellar nanocarriers for CQ and PQ drugs [Figure 7].

A-SYNTHESIS

B- ^1H NMR

Bis(alkyne) pluronic

HDLDBC-bGMPA

D- FTIR

C- ^{13}C NMR

E- SEC

Figure 7: (a) Synthesis of HDLDBC-bGMPA, (b) chemical characterization by ^1H NMR, (c) ^{13}C NMR, (d) FTIR and (e) SEC (Size exclusion chromatography). Reprinted from Ref.78; Cros *et al.*, Biomaterials science, 2019; 7:1661, Copyright (2019), with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Rhodamine labeling method was used to explore the specific targeting behaviour of these nanocarriers. Fluorescence microscopy results revealed that both DHP-bMPA and HDLDBC-bGMPA were integrated in by human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC). Furthermore,

these nanocarriers were tested for their capacity to inhibit Plasmodium growth either *in vitro* or *in vivo*. Sadrabadi *et al.* investigated the self-assembly of Pluronic F127 with dendritic polyethylene (dPE) chains resulting in the formation of spherical nanocapsules (NCs) [74]. The high encapsulation susceptibility of dPE/Pluronic-based NCs was attributed to the hydrophobic core and hydrophilic shell-like structure of dPE-Pluronics respectively. Moreover, to specify the effect of PEGylated dPE, dPE/Pluronic NCs were loaded with different concentrations of the hydrophobic anticancer drug PTX. NCs formed through microfluidics were found to have slower and more sustained release rate than the bulk synthesized NCs. This method can be extended for the formation of other types of modified, drug-loaded, dPE-based NCs with various shells in the emerging field of nanomedicine.

2.4 Cubosomes functionalized Pluronics

Cubosomes, bicontinuous cubic lyotropic liquid crystalline colloidal particles, have gained utmost attention due to their potential uses in the field of nanomedicine [75-76]. Cubosome dispersions mainly consist of amphiphilic lipids and to maintain its stability, lipid must be dispersed in excess water in the presence of a stabilizer [77]. One of the major issues to use cubosomes in the field of nanomedicine is the preservation of their morphology and internal structure after storage and cargos loading [78]. To overcome these disadvantages, Pluronics have been generally used as stabilizers. Murgia and colleagues modified the monoolein-based cubosomes with a hydrocarbon chain of Pluronics to increase the encapsulation efficiency of two fluorescent probes fluorescein and dansyl within the monoolein palisade [79]. Cubosomes were prepared by dispersing appropriate amount of monoolein in a solution of Pluronic F108 in the absence and presence of the fluorescent probes using an ultrasonic processor. The results demonstrated that monoolein and Pluronic F108 based cubosomes efficiently coupled with fluorescent probes and loaded with an anticancer drug quercetin (QCT) while retaining their inner structure. Fluorescein probe modified cubosomes can successfully be employed for single

living cell imaging. In line with this study, the same research group exploited the fluorescent dansyl conjugated Pluronic F108 to stabilize an aqueous dispersion of monoolein based cubosomes [80]. The morphology and topology were not significantly affected by the presence of fluorescent molecules. It was observed that the fluorescently labelled Pluronic F108 and the pure Pluronic F108 act as effective stabilizer for aqueous cubosome formulations which was further used to deliver QCT drug. Microscopic observations on HeLa cell cultures proved their effective internalization and high biocompatibility. Caltagirone *et al.* developed a new type of cubosome employing mixtures of Pluronic F108 and FA conjugated Pluronic F108 in appropriate ratios to incorporate Camptothecin, an anticancer drug and squarain-based NIR-emitting fluorescent probe simultaneously [81]. The physicochemical characterization of aqueous dispersions of cubosomes was performed using state-of-the-art techniques such as Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and cryo-TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy).

Figure 8 showed the Cryo TEM images of the MO-based cubosomes stabilized by the mixture F108 and FA conjugated F108 (80:20) loaded with both the dye and Camptothecin drug. Photophysical characterization proved that these cubosomes may be exploited for *in vivo* imaging purposes. The specific delivery of folate-conjugated Pluronic F108 functionalized cubosomes has been investigated via lipid droplet alterations induced in HeLa cells upon exposure to

Figure 8: Cryo-TEM image of MO-based cubosomes accommodating both the drug and the dye and stabilized by the mixture F108/F108-FA (80:20). Reprinted from Ref. 86; Caltagirone *et al.*, *Langmuir*, 2014; 21: 6228, Copyright (2014) American Chemical Society.

targeted (folate conjugated Pluronic F108 functionalized cubosomes) and nontargeted cubosomes (Pluronic F108 functionalized cubosomes). Deshpande *et al.* prepared monoolein cubosomes using Pluronic F127 as stabilizer, the surface of these cubosomes have been modified through adsorption of cationic poly- ϵ -lysine [82]. These cubosomes exhibited appreciable stability in serum solution and were readily internalized by HeLa cells. The monolayer of P ϵ L on the cubosomes facilitate the sustained drug release behaviour of encapsulated hydrophilic drug Naproxen (Nap) Functionalization of P ϵ L on cubosomes allowed the convenient chemical conjugation on their surface without disturbing their internal

Figure 9: (a) SAXS pattern for the cubosomes and the bulk phase (BP) before and after loading with hydrophobic (NR) and hydrophilic (Nap) molecules: BP loaded with NR, BP loaded with Nap sodium, BP loaded with NR and Nap sodium. Cryo-TEM for (b) cubosomes (c) Nap and NR loaded cubosomes and (d) Nap and Nile Red loaded, P ϵ L coated cubosomes, authors used RF for cubosomes here. Reprinted from Ref. 87; Deshpande *et al.*, ACS applied materials & interfaces, 2014; 19: 17126, Copyright (2014) American Chemical Society.

microstructure. Moreover, the simultaneous loading of hydrophobic dye, Nile red (NR) and Nap in cubosomes enable to use them in theranostic applications. The prepared cubosomes were characterized using SAXS and cryo-TEM [Figure 9]. Interestingly, Cubosomes

loaded with Nap revealed appreciable anticancer activity, Nap and NR loaded cubosomes

showed pronounced apoptosis in HeLa cells as compared to free Nap. Furthermore, the same research group explored the internalization mechanism of cubosomes in the Hela cancer cells

lines [83]. For this purpose, uncoated and P ϵ L coated cubosomes have been loaded with fluorescent probe NR. The results demonstrated that the surface architecture of cubosomes affect the cellular uptake mechanism. The uncoated cubosomes entered in Hela cells by an energy-independent, cholesterol-dependent mechanism; however, P ϵ L-coated cubosomes followed energy-dependent mechanisms to enter the endosomes. Drugs can be delivered through endosomal entrapment with the help of cubosomes because of their flexibility and capability to enter cells by different mechanisms. It was suggested that not only surface functionality of NPs influences the interaction with biological system, but surface architecture also plays a major role. Liver targeting of 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) loaded cubosomes formulation have been reported by Nasr and co-worker, cubosomes typically consist aqueous system of Pluronic F127 and monoolein [84]. *In vitro* drug release study evidenced that in the first hour, 50 % 5-FU release from cubosomes was released after which a slow 5-FU was sustained. However, *in vivo* biodistribution results demonstrated a significant (5-folds) increase in 5-FU liver concentration through cubosomes formulation as compared to 5-FU solution. Besides this, the histopathology and serum analysis showed more hepatocellular damage in rats administered with cubosomal formulation. These results indicated that the prepared cubosomes formulation can be used for the targeted delivery of anti-cancer drugs in liver cancer with further studies. Rarokar and colleagues prepared thermoresponsive and controlled release cubosomal formulation loaded with docetaxel (DTX) [85]. The dilution method was employed to prepare cubosomal formulation following the homogenization utilizing Pluronic F127, glyceryl monooleate and ethanol in distilled water. A gelling system comprising different ratios of Pluronic F127 and Pluronic F68 was prepared to make a thermoresponsive depot system which was incorporated within the cubosome dispersion. The thermoresponsive cubosomal formulation showed a dual property *i.e.*, gels at higher temperature and free flowing liquids at room temperature that form a stable depot in aqueous environment. The results of *in-vitro* drug-

release from cubosomal formulation, before incorporation into the gelling system, showed the approximately 97% release in 12 h. However, a burst release of approx. 21 % was observed followed by only 39% drug over a period of 12 h after incorporation into a thermoresponsive depot system, suggesting its potential as a controlled drug delivery system. Janakiraman and colleagues synthesized methotrexate (MTX) loaded cubosomes stabilized by Pluronic F127 using lipid emulsification coupled with high-pressure homogenization technique [86]. The presence of Pluronic F127 enhanced the permeability of MTX as confirmed by *in vitro* and *in vivo* anti-arthritic study. Yasser and coworkers reported an oral tablet based on cubosome dispersions using emulsification of monoglyceride stabilized by the 5% Pluronic F127 for the delivery of Telmisartan (TEL) drug [87]. Optimized cubosomal tablets were selected for *in vivo* studies which included oral administration of the formulations to albino rabbits, where a threefold increase in TEL absorption was observed. Said *et al.* designed voriconazole loaded cubosomal formulations comprising monoolein and Pluronic F127 for ocular delivery using central composite face-centred design [88]. Similarly, Rapalli *et al.* delineated the Cubosomal gels consist of Glycerol monooleate and Pluronic F127 for the topical delivery of ketoconazole designed by Quality by Design' (QbD) approach [89]. Furthermore, Malheiros *et al.* reported phytantriol-based cubosomes stabilized using Pluronic F127 for drug delivery applications and characterized using SAXS, DLS, cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM) and nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) [90]. Eldeeb and colleagues enhanced the ocular delivery of a hydrophilic drug Brimonidine tartrate (BRT) using Pluronic F127 stabilized cubosomes to and assessed it with ex-vivo permeation and *in-vivo* pharmacodynamic studies [91]. Patil *et al.* developed mucoadhesive cubosomes comprising Glycerol mono-oleate and Pluronic F127 to escalate the donepezil drug delivery to the brain [92]. Prepared cubosomes formulations were assessed for particle size, poly dispersity index, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, TEM, *in vitro* drug release and *in vivo* bio-distribution studies in rat model. Laithy and co-worker

reported on procubosome tablet formulation consisting of Glyceryl monooleate and Pluronic F127 to increase the dissolution and bioavailability of clopidogrel bisulfate drug [93]. Mohsen and colleagues explored cubosomes composed of Pluronic F127 and glyceryl monooleate to escalate the aqueous solubility of antioxidative drug Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) [94]. Hepatoprotective activity of CoQ10 loaded cubosomes was potentially enhanced by altering various enzymes activity as determined on thioacetamide (TAA) induced hepatotoxicity in Wistar rats.

2.5 Drug conjugated functionalized Pluronics

Drug conjugated Pluronics also known as Prodrug Pluronic micelles are class of drug delivery system in which a drug is covalently conjugated to either hydrophilic or hydrophobic shells. The direct conjugation of a drug to Pluronic micelles has several advantages such as high drug loading, high stability, sustained release of drug, protecting drugs from degradation, improving bioavailability and plasma half-life, improving water solubility to hydrophobic drugs, increasing site specific delivery, pharmacokinetics, and decreasing the immunogenic property [95-101]. In this context, Rafael *et al.* chemically modified Pluronic F127 with the anticancer drug Cetuximab (CET) for targeted delivery of siRNAs into breast cancer cells [102]. Pluronic F127 carboxylation was achieved through the maleic anhydride reaction followed by the conjugation of CET. CET is an epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) inhibitor used in various cancer therapies. CET-functionalized Pluronic micelles showed higher rate of cell internalization in EGFR expressing breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231) compared to non-functionalized Pluronic micelles. Fang *et al.* covalently conjugated CUR to hydrophilic terminals of Pluronic F68 chains through cis-aconitic anhydride linkers (Cis) to obtain an acid-responsive CUR system [103]. *In vitro* cytotoxic results showed higher anticancer activity of F68-Cis-CUR micelles on A2780 (the human ovarian carcinoma) and SMMC 7721 (hepatocellular carcinoma) cell lines than pure CUR. Increased cellular uptake of CUR was

observed in the case of F68-Cis-CUR micelles compared to bare CUR by way of caveolae-mediated endocytosis in an energy-dependent manner. Jeong and co-worker synthesized Pluronic F127 multicolor fluorescent NPs (F127-FNPs) by a carbonization method using an acidic catalyst [104]. The presence of hydroxyl (OH) and carboxyl (COOH) groups on the surface of F127-FNPs was determined using $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and XPS measurements. Continuing with this research, Kang *et al.* from the same research group used OH and COOH moieties to conjugate FA and DOX with acid-labile hydrazone bond [105]. The resulted carbonized Pluronic showed substantially higher decay time following the conjugation with FA and DOX. The pH-responsive hydrazone structure led to DOX release from the F127-FNPs carrier under acidic physiological conditions such as an endosomal compartment within a tumour site. *In vitro* cellular uptake, cytotoxicity with bio-imaging behaviour of DOX/FA-conjugated F127-FNPs was determined on MDCK and KB cancer cell lines. Nguyen and co-worker synthesized FA targeted bioreducible Pluronic anchored DOX micelles to target cancer cells [106]. The acrylic acid (AA) group was introduced on the hydrophobic blocks of the amine-terminated Pluronic F127 (F127-NH₂). AA-Pluronic-NH₂ was anchored to hydrazine, FA and CYS followed by conjugation of DOX through an acid-labile hydrazone bond (FA-Pluronic-C/H-DOX). The FA-Pluronic-C/H-DOX micelles showed higher cytotoxicity as compared to nontargeted micelles. Cai and colleagues have prepared Pluronic F68-CUR micelles via esterification and the solvent evaporation method [107]. These micelles showed an optimal hydrodynamic size, physical stability and high drug loading efficiency with excellent sustained release behaviour. Pluronic F68-CUR conjugates enhanced the pro-apoptotic effect of CUR on MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line. Liang *et al.* reported the synthesis of pH sensitive DTX conjugated Pluronic P123 micelles via acid-cleavage hydrazone bonds [108]. TEM and DLS techniques were employed for the characterization of prepared nano-micelles. These nano micelles were stable in rat plasma and showed pH dependent DTX release. Nguyen and co-

worker prepared the mixed micelles of Pluronic F127 and reverse Pluronic 10R5 in which FA and QCT was anchored to F127 and 10R5 respectively [109]. The prepared systems showed the enhanced DOX loading capacity and slower drug release behaviour due to the QCT conjugated Pluronics. Park *et al.* synthesized Chlorin e6 (Ce6) anchored Pluronic F127 (F127/Ce6) conjugates by esterification to improve the tumour specific delivery [110]. The two different conjugates [F127/Ce6-1 and F127/Ce6-2] were prepared and separated using hydrophobic interaction chromatography (HIC). Pluronic F127/Ce6-1 conjugates exhibited increased cellular internalization in mouse colon tumour (CT-26) cells and cellular phototoxicity as compared to free Ce6 *in vitro*. Moreover, a tumour specific Ce6-1 distribution was observed with intravenous injection of F127/Ce6-1 conjugates into tumour-bearing mice. Chen and colleagues developed the mixed micelles of Pluronic F127 and Pluronic P105 conjugated with MTX [F127/P105-MTX] employing the thin-film hydration method [111]. F127/P105-MTX enhanced drug loading capacity as compared to physically entrapped MTX mixed micelles. A sustained, pH-dependent MTX release and increased blood circulation time was observed from F127/P105-MTX. Furthermore, F127/P105-MTX showed increased accumulation and marked antitumour activity against KBv MDR tumour as compared to MTX injection. Xu and colleagues prepared prodrug mixed micelles composed of Pluronic F127 and P123 to abrogate the tumour MDR [112]. In the prepared system, F127 was modified with phenylboric acid (PBA) and P123 (FBP-CAD) was conjugated with DOX. *In vitro* studies revealed the marked increase in the cellular uptake and drug concentration of FBP-CAD in MCF-7/ADR breast cancer cells. *In vivo* study observes the enhanced DOX accumulation at tumour sites along with increased tumour growth inhibition due to the anti-MDR effect of P123 and decreased side effects to normal organs. Ma *et al.* reported the synthesis of DOX conjugated Pluronic F127 micellar system via acid-sensitive cis-aconityl linkage (F127-CS-DOX) [113]. Subsequently, a pH-sensitive F127-CS-DOX conjugate was loaded with PTX for

the co-delivery of DOX and PTX. A pH dependent drug release was evident from the *in vitro* drug release study. Furthermore, *in vivo* pharmacokinetic study in rats demonstrated elevated values of PTX and DOX for PTX- loaded F127-CS-DOX micelles as that of those for PTX plus DOX solution. Zhang and co-worker developed a photo-cleavable coumarin linkage (CM) mediated local anaesthetic drug tetracaine (T) conjugated to Pluronic F127 (F127-CM-T) through alkyne-azide click reaction depicted in **Figure 10** [114]. F127-CM-T prodrug system showed local anaesthetic effect only after irradiation with a low-power blue light emitting diode (LED), resulting in local anaesthesia.

Figure 10: (a) Synthesis of F127-CM-T through alkyne-azide click reaction, (b) Photo-cleavage reaction of F127-CM-T, (c) ¹H NMR of F127-CM-T. Reprinted from Ref. 119, Zhang *et al.*, Nature communications, 2020;11:1, Copyright (2020) Nature Publisher.

2.6 Polysaccharide functionalized Pluronics:

Polysaccharides, are the natural class of biopolymers existing in nature, that play significant roles in the biology of living organisms [115]. Apart from that Polysaccharides got attention in drug delivery systems due to its multiple advantages such as non-toxicity, stability, hydrophilicity, and biodegradability [116,117]. Polysaccharides are studied with different Pluronics to fabricate more advantageous drug delivery systems with enhanced biocompatibility, drug loading capacity and many more. Khaliq and colleagues reported the Pluronic F68 coated heparin NPs for the chemo-photodynamic combination cancer therapy using drug DOX and methylene blue (MB) [115]. Electrostatic interactions between heparin and DOX, MB enable the loading within NPs and Pluronic F68 provide the stabilisation to NPs. These NPs exhibited tumour targeting and antitumour efficacy tested in tumour-bearing mice. Tong et al. reported the heparin conjugated Pluronic F127 nanocomplexes for the delivery of Cisplatin [116]. Obtained nanocomplex showed the slower release of Cisplatin as well as their antiproliferation in lung cancer cell line (NCI-H460) and antitumor activity *in vivo*. Pluronic F127 grafted Pullulan (polysaccharide polymer) with pendant carboxymethyl groups (CMP) have been used to develop the hydrogels for the antibiotic Amoxicillin delivery. An and colleagues reported the gels composed of Carboxymethyl Cellulose (CMC), Pluronic and Pullulan for tissue regeneration as well as enhance antiadhesion activities [117]. These antiadhesion formulation showed remarkable stability over 30 days in the operative sites without any toxicity and side effects. Silva *et al.* communicated the interactional study between mucoadhesive polysaccharides *viz.* sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose cellulose (HPMC) with Pluronic F127 [118]. Interactions of NaCMC and HPMC with Pluronic F127 resulted in the decrease in the *cmc* of F127 as well as increase in the hydrodynamic diameter of aggregates. Multiple techniques such as DSC, SEM and TEM were utilized to characterize these aggregates. Moreover, Erythrosine (ERI) a hydrophilic drug was loaded in this polymeric composite and *in vitro* drug release was demonstrated. Gel comprising hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC)- α -cyclodextrin (α CD) with Pluronic P123 were evaluated to solubilize the antifungal drug Griseofulvin. Hen's Egg Test-Chorioallantoic Membrane (HET-CAM) test evidenced that the fabricated hydrogels have the excellent biocompatibility [119]. Furthermore, the Griseofulvin loaded gels exhibited the antifungal activity against *Trichophyton rubrum* and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. Nguyen and co-worker prepared biotin-conjugated chitosan-Pluronic P123 for the delivery system of PTX [120]. Moreover, formulations exhibited the sustained PTX release and release was

controlled by the pH of the medium. Prepared formation showed the good biological compatibility with a human foreskin fibroblast cell line and manifested good internalization efficiency in MCF-7 cells. Haseeb *et al.* developed a nanoparticulate system in which Linseed polysaccharides were used as core to load drug DTX and Pluronic F-68 act as shell [121]. Authors emphasized that these Pluronic-polysaccharide nano-formulations will have wide scope for delivering anticancer therapeutic agents. Bhattacharya and colleagues reported the delivery of thymoquinone drug by using hyaluronic acid (HA)-functionalized Pluronic P123 and F127 mixed micelles for the treatment of triple-negative breast cancer (MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-468) [122]. Dual drug delivery system is also important class, in this regard, Joung and co-workers reported the Heparin-Conjugated Pluronic Nanogels for the delivery of DNase and PTX; which showed enhanced encapsulation efficiency, and intracellular uptake in HeLa cells [123]. Nguyen *et al.* fabricated the thermoresponsive heparin-Pluronic F127 nanogel system for the co-delivery of CIS and CUR. Dual drug loaded nanogel system showed anti-proliferative ability to the MCF-7 cell line. Authors emphasized that codelivery can prove as remedy to circumvent the problems associated in cancer chemotherapy with this type of nanopatform delivery system [124].

2.7 Biotin functionalized Pluronics:

Biotin (also known as vitamin B₇) is widely used to target specific cancer cells as biotin-specific receptors such as avidin, neutravidin, and streptavidin are overexpressed on cancer cell lines that can be targeted through Biotin functionalized NPs [125]. Biotin functionalized Pluronics are extensively studied for targeted delivery of anticancer drugs. Russo *et al.* used Pluronic P123-F127 mixed micelles to deliver Niclosamide (NCL) to treat multidrug resistant non-small lung cancer. Biotin was functionalized with Pluronic F127 while rhodamine B (fluorescent active) was tagged with Pluronic P123, Biotin-decorated mixed micelles enable to internalized more efficiently than plain Pluronic mixed micelles in A549 lung cancer cell line [126]. Rhodamine B tethered Pluronic P123-Biotin functionalized Pluronic F127 mixed micelles were further utilized for the photodynamic therapy of Verteporfin (VER) drug in PC3 (Prostatic Small Cell Carcinoma) and MCF-7 cancer cells by Pellosi and co-workers [127]. Rhodamine B insertion enable to monitor intracellular distribution and uptake of nano-formulation in the cell lines. VER loaded mixed micelles demonstrated a larger intracellular distribution as well as photosensitising effect than pure VER drug confirmed from confocal microscopy. Nguyen and colleagues used polymeric micelles made up of chitosan-Pluronic P123-biotin (Cs-P123-Bio) copolymer for the targeted delivery of PTX on human breast

cancer cells (MCF-7). Cs–P123-Biotin showed excellent biological compatibility with a human foreskin fibroblast cell line as well as improved internalization efficiency in MCF-7 cell line. Xiong *et al.* functionalized biotin with PLA tethered Pluronic F127 (Biotin-F127–PLA) to develop targeted nanoparticle system for PTX [128]. *in vitro* and *in vivo* findings confirmed that Biotin-F127–PLA NPs specifically target human ovarian cancer OVCAR-3 cells (CA-125 positive) than SKOV-3 cells (CA-125 negative) [129]. Same research group also used Biotin functionalized Pluronic F87/PLA and Pluronic P85/PLA) for the delivery of PTX in ovarian cancer treatment [130]. Zhu and colleagues exploited the BIOTIN-modified oligochitosan-F127 conjugate (F127-CS-BIOTIN) NPs for the loading of Honokiol (HON), a natural anticancer drug [131]. It was observed that Biotin functionalization guided the HON loaded F127-CS-Biotin formulation and resulted in more easily uptake in the tumour cells than biotin-unmodified F127-CS.

Table 1: Functionalization of Pluronics with different moieties and their targeted drug delivery use in animal and cell line models

Functionalization	Payload	Pluronics	Targeted disease and cell lines
Redox sensitive (disulphide linked)	TOC, RES, DOX, Brusatol, BA, SiRNA	F127, F108, F68,	Bel 7402 (liver cancer), MCF-7, MDA-MB-231 (breast cancer), HeLa cells (cervical cancer) and bone marrow derived BMSCs [29-36]
Folic acid (FA)	PTX, Cde/ZnS, DOX, BOSA and NPAPF, Coumarin-6, Insulin, Fisetin, SLB	P105/L101, F127, P123, L121, F87, P85	MCF-7/ADR cells (breast cancer), C6 glioma cells, OVCAR-3 (ovarian cancer cells), ovarian cancer cells, Liver cancer cells [41-55]
Dendrimers (PAMAM, LPEI and PPI)	DOX, gene, PTX, Propranolol, Cyclosporin A, CUR, CQ and PQ	F127, P123, F68	Fibroblast cells, MCF-7/ADR cells (breast cancer), MCF-7 (breast cancer), C2C12 myoblasts and CHO cells, human colon adenocarcinoma cell line (Caco-2), Plasmodium infected red blood cells (PRBCs) [63-74]
Cubosomes	QCT, Camptothecin, 5-FU, Nap, NR, DTX, MTX, TEL, Ketoconazole, Brimonidine	F108, F127, F68	HeLa cells (cervical cancer), arthritis, Thioacetamide induced hepatotoxicity in rats [79-94]

	tartrate (BRT), Donepezil, Clopidogrel bisulfate, CoQ10		
Drug	Cetuximab (CET), siRNA, CUR, QCT, DTX, Ce6, MTX, DOX, PTX, Tetracaine (T)	F127, P105, P123	MDA-MB-231 (breast cancer), A2780 (the human ovarian carcinoma) and SMMC 7721 (hepatocellular carcinoma) cell lines, MCF-7/ADR (breast cancer), KBv MDR tumour, CT-26 (mouse colon tumour), MDCK and Kb cancer cells [102-114]
Polysaccharides	DOX and MB, CIS, ERI, Griseofulvin. DTX, Thymoquinone, PTX and DNase, CIS and CUR	F68, F127, P123	Antitumour activity in mice, Trichophyton rubrum and Trichophyton mentagrophytes. MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-468, HeLa cells, MCF-7 cells [115-124]
Biotin	NCL, VER, PTX, HON	P123, F127, P85, F87, F127	Non-small lung cancer, A549 lung cancer cell line, PC3 and MCF-7, OVCAR-3 and SKOV-3 cells [126-131]

3.0 Pluronics functionalized with nanoparticles:

NPs are known for their application in biotechnology, nanomedicine, but issues are encountered in their stability, solubility in biological fluids, toxicity, biocompatibility and biodegradability. Functionalization of Pluronics with NPs provide stability and decrease the NPs toxicity by virtue of providing biocompatible stealth due to an ethylene oxide region on the surface especially in metal NPs. This results in simultaneously enhanced therapeutic efficacy of drug molecules and other bioactive molecules by improving their solubilization, their bioavailability, their interaction with biological media, their adsorption to specific cells or tissues, and intracellular penetration. Moreover, nanoparticle functionalization also stabilizes Pluronic micelles and enhance their retention *in vivo* [132-135]. In this context, three NPs namely, iron oxide (magnetic) NPs, Gold NPs and silica NPs have been extensively

functionalized with different Pluronics for their use in drug delivery, these approaches will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

3.1 Functionalization of Pluronic with Magnetic nanoparticles:

Iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) NPs generally refer as magnetic NPs have gained utmost attention in the field of drug delivery, hyperthermia treatment and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) due to their straightforward synthesis and superparamagnetic properties [136,137]. Site specific delivery of drugs (or any other bioactive molecule) can be achieved by guiding drug loaded magnetic NPs using an external magnetic field [138-141]. To circumvent the problems associated with magnetic NPs (as discussed in the **Section 3.0** of metal NPs), researchers have used multiple techniques in which NPs are coated with Pluronics as alternatives [142,143]. The coating of Pluronics provide the greater stability as well as high biocompatibility by effectively preventing aggregation, the adsorption of proteins [144,145]. Chen *et al.* developed a temperature responsive magnetic nanoparticle from iron oxide NPs and poly(ethyleneimine)-modified Pluronic P123 [146]. DLS measurements revealed that hydrodynamic diameter of the magnetic NPs experienced a sharp decrease from 45 to 25 nm while the temperature was elevated from 20 to 35°C. The opening and closing mechanism of these NPs at different temperatures enabled the loading and release of both hydrophobic and hydrophilic model drugs ibuprofen (IBU) and eosin yellow. In line with the previous report, Bhattacharya and colleagues reported a dual temperature and pH responsive polymer integrated magnetic NPs composed of polyethyleneimine (PEI) cross-linked Pluronic F127 and mixed ferrite NPs for MRI and the delivery of DOX [147]. EDC (1-[3-(dimethylamino)- propyl]-3-ethyl carbodiimide hydrochloride)/NHS (N-hydroxysuccinimide) coupling was employed to cross-link the dual responsive PEI/Pluronic F127 with citrate stabilized mixed ferrite NPs. In order to accomplish cancer targeting and imaging capability, both FA and rhodamine isothiocyanate (RITC) were conjugated to NPs. DOX loaded FA targeted NPs (DOX-FA-Poly-MFNPs) retained their

stealthy structure under physiological conditions but at acidic pH (5.0), the DOX–FA–Poly-MFNPs exhibited enhanced release of DOX. These DOX–FA–Poly-MFNPs displayed effective therapeutic activity evaluated by a cytotoxicity assay and cell cycle analysis in HeLa cells. Barick and co-worker developed the Pluronic P123 stabilized Fe_3O_4 magnetic NPs for delivery of the hydrophobic drug CUR [148]. Functionalization of NPs with P123 was confirmed by FTIR, TGA, DLS, UV-visible spectroscopy and zeta-potential measurements.

Figure 11: Schematic illustration of Pluronic P123 stabilized HMNPs (PSMNPs) and photographs showing the change of HMNPs from hydrophobic to hydrophilic, Reprinted from Ref.136; Barick *et al.*, *RSC Advances*, 2016; 6: 98674, Copyright (2016) Royal Society of Chemistry.

PSMNPs were developed by introducing Pluronic P123 onto the surface of hydrophobic magnetic NPs (HMNPs) as shown in **Figure 11**. The insertion of Pluronic P123 provided a hydrophobic interface for CUR loading with enhanced colloidal stability and biocompatibility. Moreover, PSMNPs exhibited high CUR loading capacity and pH dependent release behaviour into the tumour cells. Nano-drug delivery platform consisting of titania nanotube arrays have been loaded with the indomethacin drug encapsulated Pluronic F127 micelles and magnetic NPs [149]. A rapid triggered release (100% release) of the indomethacin drug from Pluronic F127 micelles was achieved by activating the magnetic NPs loaded at the bottom of these titania nanotubes. Encapsulation of EDTA capped Fe_3O_4 NPs in Pluronic F127 micelles have been reported by Shah and colleagues [150]. These magnetic micelles were loaded with hydrophobic drug imatinib in which EDTA capped Fe_3O_4 NPs act as core and Pluronic F127

act as the shell of nano formulation. *In vitro* study in human bone marrow K562 cell-line revealed that the cellular internalization imatinib loaded magnetic micelles was higher than the free imatinib. *In vivo* distribution pattern of imatinib loaded Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle-based magnetic micelles showed that a higher amount of drug in bone marrow than liver and blood plasma. Noh *et al.* developed Pluronic F127 coated Fe₃O₄ NPs coupled with brain tumour targeted Tat peptide and transferrin (Tf) through noncovalent conjugation of dopamine terminal and Fe₃O₄ NPs [151]. A photosensitizing antitumour drug Ce6 was loaded in the core-shell interface of the NPs. Tf receptor-mediated endocytosis and Tat peptide-mediated cellular interaction of these Y shaped ligands resulted in the enhancement of *in vitro/in vivo* cellular uptake of these NPs. When illuminated, these Ce6-loaded NPs evidenced significant enhancement of U87-MG cell ablation. Wu *et al.* designed PTX-loaded charge-switchable nanohybrid system, provoked by the low pH value (pH 6.5) of the tumour microenvironment [152]. The nanohybrid system showed an enhancement of T2-MR imaging and anticancer activity. PTX loaded nanohybrid system consisted of two different functional parts (a) a Pluronic F127 which acted as a nanocarrier for PTX and magnetite nanocluster after self-assembly in an aqueous solution; (b) a hydrophilic polymeric shell obtained from stearyl-polyethylenimine-2,3-dimethylmalefic anhydride. *In vitro* Prussian blue staining of HepG2 cells demonstrated that the response of PTX loaded nanohybrid system to a low pH value (pH 6.5) of the tumour microenvironment could enhance the uptake efficiency by the tumour cells results in the enhancement in the MR imaging ability of the densely packed superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticle. Hu and colleagues designed and fabricated yolk/shell capsules consisting of a hydrophobic transformable magnetic core, thermally responsive Pluronic F68, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and an ultra-thin silica shell [153]. The nanospheres were characterized using DLS and temperature dependant change in size was observed. These capsules can trigger burst IBU release through an external magnetic field by the hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic transition of Pluronic F68 that

result in size contraction at about CMT as shown in **Figure 12**. Huang *et al.* synthesized the multifunctional temperature-responsive magnetic micelles by conjugating the polylactic acid ligated Pluronic F127 pentablock copolymer with superparamagnetic iron oxide NPs [154]. These magnetic micelles loaded with DOX and its release behaviour can be controlled by environmental pH and the external magnetic fields. Results of Alamar blue assay confirmed

Figure 12: Cumulative drug release of F68/PVA nanospheres (b) DLS results of F68/PVA nanospheres showing decrease in diameter abruptly at about CMT. (c) Cumulative release profiles of IBU triggered by a high frequency magnetic field (d) After the exposure with magnetic field, capsules rupture due to the volume/hydrophobicity transition of cores as demonstrated in TEM image. Reprinted from Ref. 141, Hu *et al.*, Chemical Communication, 2011;47, 1776, Copyright (2011), with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

that these drug-loaded magnetic micelles have excellent biocompatibility as well as antiproliferative activity. Tomitaka *et al.* reported Pluronic F127 coated Fe_3O_4 NPs for hyperthermia treatment [155]. Appropriate temperature rise was achieved under an ac magnetic field of 16 kA/m (200 Oe) and 20 kA/m (250 Oe) at 210 kHz. *In vitro* hyperthermia treatment of Pluronic-coated Fe_3O_4 NPs reduced the viability of HeLa cancer cells. Qin and co-worker

developed a new ferrogel consist of Pluronic F127 and superparamagnetic iron oxide NPs (SPIONs) and subsequently loaded with drug indomethacin [156]. These water-soluble SPIONs were emersed in concentrated Pluronic F127 solution cooled at 4°C ; upon increase in temperature, gelation occurred and the F127 micelles arranged in an ordered structure. The PEO comprising hydrophilic corona region acted as the scaffold of the ferrogel, while PPO

forming hydrophobic core solubilized indomethacin depicted in **Figure 13 (a)**. The exertion of magnetic field (**Figure 13(b)**) led to contraction of ferrogel, resulting in generation of concentration gradient between PPO cores and water channels leading to an increase in the local concentration of indomethacin, thus accelerating its release. Heggannavar and colleagues reported the magnetic mesoporous NPs fabricated with Pluronic F127 conjugated with Tf to achieve the sustained targeted release of DOX [157]. The cytotoxicity study was performed in

Figure 13: Schematic representation of ordered microstructure of SPEL (Pluronic F127 and SPIONs): a) before applying the magnetic field, Indomethacin encapsulated in the hydrophobic moiety of micelles; b) after magnetic field, SPIONs orient and approach each other, shrinking the micelles and leading to accelerated Indomethacin release. Corresponding photographs of SPEL in a capillary c) before and d) after applying a magnetic field. Reprinted from Ref. 144, Qin *et al.*, *Advanced Materials*, 2009;21, 1354, Copyright (2009) Wiley.

U87 cell line and IC_{50} value (0.570 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of Tf-conjugated NPs was found to be significantly different as that of pure NPs (121.98 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Tf-conjugated NPs showed an admirable BBB permeability, enhanced by applying external magnetic field, thus indicating the increased uptake of drugs in U87 cells. Lin *et al.* investigated loading of the

hydrophobic dye NR into Pluronic F127 micelles decorated with water-soluble polyacrylic acid-bound iron oxides (PAAIO) and their MRI properties [158]. PAAIO maintained its superparamagnetic characteristics even after the encapsulation of NR, therefore, can be employed for MRI. Subsequently, FA was functionalized on Pluronic F127-PAAIO to produce FA-PF127-PAAIO to specifically target cancer cells. Higher intracellular uptake was obtained using FA-PF127-PAAIO into KB cells, confirmed from laser confocal scanning microscopy (CLSM), flow cytometry, and atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) techniques. *In vitro* MRI

study conferred that excellent T2-weighted imaging is possible with FA-PF127-PAAIO since it showed negligible cytotoxicity. To investigate magneto-chemotherapy, Salunkhe *et al.* prepared Pluronic F127-SPIONs NPs for the loading of DOX. MRI guided magneto-chemotherapy exhibited more than 96% cell death in MCF-7 cells [159].

3.2 Functionalization of Pluronic with Gold nanoparticles

Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) are of significant interest for drug delivery and biomedical applications due to their significant surface modifiability and unique size; one hundred to ten thousand less than the human cells which facilitate its interactions with biomolecules *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. Despite their widespread application, GNPs have several issues such as poor drug loading capacity as well as the challenge to enhance the biocompatibility for the living cells for potential use in nanomedicine and biomedical fields. Researchers corroborated that after functionalization of these NPs with biocompatible polymers, these problems can be overcome with Pluronics due to their unique thermo-responsive properties, biocompatibility, enhanced stability, drug loading capacity and cellular uptake [160-164]. In 2006, Bae *et al.* designed thermosensitive GNPs by cross-linking them with the shell of Pluronic F127. Thiol-functionalization of terminal hydroxyl groups of Pluronic F127 was performed which allowed the self-assembly of Pluronic micelles in aqueous solution with unveiled-SH groups in the outer layer of the shell. GNPs were then cross linked to the thiol groups present in the outer shell. The self-assembly of Pluronic inside the cross-linked network led to a temperature-dependent volume transition by the prepared gold-Pluronic micelles [165]. Xu and co-worker prepared nanocomposites in which Pluronic F127 was cross linked with GNPs [166]. Improved stability against dilution of Pluronic cross-linked GNPs and reassembly in the presence of trigger molecule GSH was observed, which enables its potential use in drug delivery applications. Tao *et al.* synthesized reduction-responsive Pluronic F127 and P123 conjugated GNPs for the delivery of PTX [167]. First, thiol-terminated Pluronic copolymer (F127-SH and P123-SH)

was synthesized by conjugating an amino group of CYS to a terminal hydroxyl group of Pluronic and reducing the disulfide bond. PTX loaded Pluronic F127 and P123 conjugated GNPs exhibited higher physical stability and *in vivo* pharmacokinetic activity than non-conjugated controls. Higher cellular uptake and cytotoxicity of PTX loaded Pluronic F127 and P123 conjugated GNPs in U87 (brain cancer) cell lines was confirmed by flow cytometry, fluorescence microscopy and cytotoxicity studies. Simon *et al.* reported a one-step reaction to synthesize Pluronic F127-gold hybrid NPs (GNP-F127) in aqueous solution by exploiting Pluronic F127 as both stabilizing and reducing agent [168]. The NPs are stable even in high molar NaCl solution because the concentration of Pluronic F127 are much higher than its *cmc* value. Synthesized GNP-F127 NPs were further loaded with Methylene Blue (MB) phenothiazinium based photosensitizing drug and studied for its biomedical application in both in optical imaging and drug delivery. The same research group further reported the loading of MB in highly stable Pluronic-F127 coated gold nanoaggregates (GNPA-F127) and conferring that, these nanoaggregates were highly efficient in photodynamic cancer therapy [169]. Scanning confocal surface-enhanced resonant Raman spectroscopy (SERRS) and fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) confirmed that optical imaging can be possible with these MB loaded GNPA-F127 as Raman and fluorescence signals were observed in murine colon carcinoma (C-26) cancer cell lines. Authors emphasized that MB-loaded gold nanoaggregates showed remarkable photodynamic therapeutic activity against C-26 cell lines than the free MB drug. Sun and colleagues explored Pluronic F127-b-poly(L-lysine) coated GNPs (Pluronic-PLL@Au) for the PTX delivery in chemo-photothermal therapy [170]. Prepared PTX loaded Pluronic-PLL@Au showed a greater cytotoxic effect as well as cellular uptake in MDA-MB-231 triple negative breast cancer cell line and Balb/c nude mouse than pure PTX [Figure 14]. The preparation of biogenic Pluronic F127 coated 5-FU-loaded GNPs (PFGNPs) was reported by Mahdi *et al.* [171]. Several NPs

formulations were optimized using Design Expert® software. Optimized 5-FU-loaded PFGNPs demonstrated higher stability, drug release, cytotoxicity in colon cancer cell lines than 5-FU optimum size and less hemocompatibility.

Figure 14: (a) Fluorescence microscopy images of MDA-MB-231 cells treated with Pluronic-PLL@Au, Taxol, PTX-loaded Pluronic-PLL@Au and PTX-loaded Pluronic-PLL GNPs (b) MDA-MB-231 cell viabilities at different dosages of Pluronic-PLL GNPs after 24 h incubation, with or without laser irradiation, (c) Cell viability comparison after incubation with blank Pluronic-PLL@Au, Taxol and PTX-loaded Pluronic-PLL@Au with or without laser irradiation, (d) Therapeutic efficacy versus NPs concentration for different treatments. Reprinted from Ref. 158; Sun *et al.*, *Theranostics*. 2017;7: 4424. Copyright (2017) Ivyspring International Publisher.

Furthermore, 5-FU-loaded PFGNPs showed greater (4.5-fold) *ex-vivo* permeation across the rat jejunum as compared to 5-FU. Kim *et al.* designed ROS-GSH-responsive PTX-loaded polymer dot (PD) formed by diselenide linkage and triphenylphosphonium (TPP) [172]. PD-

TPP(PTX) system released PTX into the mitochondria of cancer cells due to specificity of TPP towards mitochondria.

3.3 Functionalization of Pluronic with Silica nanoparticles:

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have been used as drug carriers and theranostic agents because of their facile surface modification, good chemical stability, high surface area and pore volume among numerous nanomaterials [173,174]. Despite these properties, coating with Pluronics is crucial to enhance their biocompatibility, stability, aqueous or biological media solubility, encapsulation capacity, to protect and transport drugs. In this regard, Espinoza *et al.* reported the synthesis of Pluronic F127 coated mesoporous silica and iron oxide NPs (MNPs-SiO₂-F127) for the delivery of DOX [173]. MNPs and MNPs-SiO₂-F127 were characterized using different techniques such as UV-visible spectroscopy, DLS, FTIR and X-ray absorption near-edge spectra (XANES), demonstrating MNPs-SiO₂-F127-4% showed significant drug encapsulation capacity. Cytotoxicity study using these prepared NPs did not show significant cell toxicity against HEK293T and HepG2 cells. Furthermore, MTT assay revealed the higher cell apoptosis of DOX loaded MNPs-SiO₂-F127 NPs in liver cancer cells. Sha and co-worker developed stable MSNs materials coated with Pluronic P123 [PMSNs] via hydrophobic interactions with octadecyl chain-modified MSNs [174]. *In vitro* release study on PMSNs with disulphide bonds evidenced redox-responsive drug release properties also on the cellular level. Furthermore, the coating of P123 resulted in anti-metastasis effect and Pluronic P123 accumulation in the tumour cells was increased due to 'EPR' effect of NPs. Yildirim *et al.* prepared Pluronic F127 and hydrophobic MSNs capped PEGylated MSNs (F127-OMSN) for DOX loading [175]. In media with high salinity, the resulting nanocarriers showed appreciable stability and dispersion as compared to uncoated MSNs. MTT assay and *in vitro* cytocompatibility study demonstrated good cytocompatibility of F127-OMSN with RBCs and MCF-7 breast cancer cells. In addition, *in vitro* drug release study showed the slow DOX

release from these F127-OMSN as compared to OMSN. Yan *et al.* prepared a hypoxia responsive azobenzene polymer deposited with Pluronic F68 conjugated MSN for the loading of photosensitizer Ce6 [176]. Coumarin 6 and rhodamine B was used as FRET donor and acceptor, respectively to observe the Ce6 release in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Furthermore, MSN loaded Ce6 was assessed for its toxicity under hypoxia conditions. It is well reported in literature that Pluronics tend to increase the permeability of lipid bilayers. Therefore, Rahman and colleagues reported the use of Pluronic L61 and L64 to modify the release of MB (a molecular indicator) from superparamagnetic MSNs coated with lipid bilayer [177]. It was observed that drug release was increased 4-fold by adding Pluronic L61 as compared to Pluronic L64 due to the lower hydrophilicity of Pluronic L61 which distorted the structure of the lipid bilayer. Xu *et al.* reported the coating of Pluronic on MSNs (PMSNs) by facilitating hydrophobic interactions with the hydrophilic segment of the Pluronic to increase the aqueous solubility of synthesized PMSNs [178]. Firstly, CUR drug was covalently conjugated with large pores of MSNs using thiol-ene “click” chemistry and later coated with F127. *In vitro* cell lines studies conferred that prepared MSNs exhibited self-fluorescent activity and high cytotoxicity in A549 lung cancer cell lines. Zhang and colleagues synthesized Pluronic P123 conjugated 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (P123-DOPE) and eventually coated it on irinotecan (CPT-11) loaded MSNs [179]. Study on breast cancer cells MCF-7/BCRP using prepared MSNs demonstrated that CPT-11 efflux mediated via by breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP) was inhibited by P123-DOPE, thus, increased the cytotoxicity effect against MCF-7/BCRP drug resistant cancer cells. Moreover, CPT-11 loaded PLS-MSNs demonstrated low toxicity and high therapeutic effect in drug resistant breast tumours bearing BALB/c nude mice. Xu *et al.* developed a self-fluorescent imaging and drug delivery system in which CUR loaded Pluronic F127 micelles were subsequently coated on MSNs through Schiff base [180]. CUR loaded Pluronic MSNs releases drug in acidic condition due to pH-

sensitive Schiff base while inhibited release of drug under natural condition. In addition, coating of CUR-F127 micelles on MSNs surface led to a significant increase in the fluorescent intensity of CUR-F127 and exhibited appreciable anti-photobleaching property. Silveira *et al.* reported the preparation of a hydrogel-based formulation consisting Pluronic F127 coated sildenafil (SIL) loaded MSNs (PF127-MSNs-SIL) [181]. Pluronic F127 coating to MSNs resulted in stabilized MSNs, sustained MSNs-SIL release and prompt gelation after intraperitoneally administered in rats as liquids. In addition, histopathological analyses of the prostate demonstrated that PF127-MSNs-SIL significantly ameliorated the chemically induced prostate cancer in rats. Prabhuraj and co-worker prepared PEG coated CUR loaded MSN and further Tf was conjugated to target human Pancreatic cancer cells [182]. The prepared MSN exhibited significantly higher anti-cancer activity in MIA PaCa-2 cells as that of free CUR.

Table 2: Overview of delivery applications of Pluronic functionalized nanoparticles

Functionalization	Payload	Plurionics	Targeted disease and cell lines
Magnetic NPs	IBU, Eosin yellow, DOX, Ce6, Indomethacin, Imatinib, PTX, NR	P123, F127, F68	HeLa cells (cervical cancer), Human bone marrow K562 cell-line, U87-MG cell (brain cancer cell lines), HepG2 cells (Human Liver Cell Lines), KB cells (tumour cell line) [146-159]
GNPs	PTX, MB, 5-FU	P123, F127,	U87 cell lines, C-26 cells (colon carcinoma cancer), MDA-MB-231 cell line (breast cancer), <i>in vivo</i> anti- cancer activity in Balb/c nude mouse, colon cancer cell lines, <i>ex-vivo</i> permeation [165-172]
Silica NPs	DOX, Ce6, MB, CUR, CPT-11, SIL	F127, P123, F68, L61, L64	HEK293T, HepG2 cells, liver cancer cells, MCF-7 cells (breast cancer), A549 cells (lung cancer cell lines), MCF-7/BCRP (breast cancer cells), breast cancer induced BALB/c nude mice, <i>in vivo</i> study in chemically induced prostate cancer in rats [173-182]

4.0 Modifying the properties of Pluronic based hydrogels

Hydrogel composites have frequently utilized in drug delivery because of their potential to absorb water and adapt similar body cell conditions [183]. Moreover, hydrogel due to its porous structure allows the high loading capacity [184]. Pluronics have by virtue the ability to transform from sol to gel via micellization and gelation in a concentration and temperature dependent manner. Pluronics have utilized in *in situ* gelling system for local or transdermal drug delivery of various drugs [185, 186]. Among all, Pluronic F127 has particularly being used because below human body temperature, it shows reverse sol–gel transition temperature property also called lower critical solution temperature (LCST) and transforms into gel state in the body at 37°C [187, 188]. However, the major disadvantage of Pluronic based gels, as sustained drug delivery carrier is the fast dissolution in the physiological environment and short residence time, thus its concentration decreases below the critical gelation concentration level [189-190]. Furthermore, these gels also have the low drug loading capacity, stability that limits their application in drug delivery [191]. Therefore, Pluronics modified gels has gained attention as focus on injectable hydrogel delivery due to improved and remarkable properties in term of stability, high loading capacity and biocompatibility [192]. In this section, we have focused on different strategies that used to modify the Pluronic based hydrogels (chitosan, photo cross-linked and HA modified hydrogels) to overcome Pluronic-associated limitations.

4.1 Pluronic-Chitosan based hydrogels:

Chitosan is a natural polymer that presents various interesting properties such as non-toxic nature in human tissue, biodegradability, biocompatibility and mucoadhesive that made it acceptable for use in drug delivery systems and biomedical or cosmetic applications [193, 194]. Ju *et al.* developed and characterized the micelles hybrid injectable hydrogels to improve the loading capacity and delivery of PTX [195]. In this hybrid hydrogel system, carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCS) diffused in P407 (Pluronic F127) gels was cross linked with glutaraldehyde

(GA) followed by the uniform dispersion of PTX loaded N-octyl-O-sulfate chitosan micelles into it. PTX loaded F127-CMCS/GA hydrogels were characterized for viscosity, mechanical properties *in vitro* and results showed the stronger mechanical properties, enhanced loading capacity and prolonged PTX release. The effect on viscosity and hardness of hydrogels were observed varying the concentration of GA [Figure 15]. Furthermore, *in vivo* tissue distribution

Figure 15. Characterization of P407 (Pluronic F127) modified hydrogels (P407-CMCS/GA). (a) Viscosities of P407 and P407-CMCS solutions (from 18 to 37°C), (b) Viscosities of P407-CMCS/GA solutions at different concentrations of GA (c) Swelling behaviours of P407-CMCS/GA hydrogels with different concentrations of GA, (d) The mechanical properties of P407-CMCS/GA hydrogels with different amounts of GA. Reprinted from Ref. 183; Ju *et al.*, Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2013;102: 2707. Copyright (2013), with permission from Elsevier.

and anticancer activity of prepared hydrogel was also evaluated in hepatoma solidity cell (Heps) tumour-bearing mice. The results evidenced a longer retention of PTX loaded F127-CMCS hydrogel at tumour sites with better tumour inhibition rate as compared to unmodified Pluronic F127 gels.

Yu and co-worker synthesized a dual pH- and temperature-responsive Pluronic F127/CMCS/GA based hydrogel system [196]. The addition of Pluronic F127 improved the biocompatibility of the hydrogel. F127-CMCS crosslinked hydrogel was characterized for its properties including rheological property, swelling ratio, cytotoxicity and *in vitro* release of nepafenac (NP). CCK-8 (Cell Counting Kit-8) assay results evidenced that F127-CMCS crosslinked hydrogels at low concentration did not show significant cytotoxicity on human corneal epithelial cells. *In vitro* drug release study observed the cumulative release of NP from the hydrogel at 35 °C and pH 7.4. Pelegriño *et al.* prepared a thermoresponsive hydrogel based on chitosan-Pluronic F127 incorporated with NO donor (GSNO) for release of nitric oxide (NO) [197]. Pluronic F127 helps in formation of hydrogel network and allows a target specific release of the NO donor/NO. At therapeutic levels, hydrogel demonstrated a constant NO/NO donor release in *in vitro* release study. Pluronic F127-GSNO hydrogel showed a synergistic effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Moreover, the prepared hydrogel did not show toxicity against mammalian cells at the concentration that was needed for an antibacterial activity. Rokhade and co-worker, developed various chitosan-Pluronic F127 hydrogels for the delivery of 5-FU using GA as crosslinking agent [198]. Hydrogel microspheres were characterized employing several techniques including UV spectroscopy, FTIR spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). UV spectroscopy results showed up to 86% 5-FU loading into hydrogel microspheres. A slow and prolonged release (up to 24 h) was observed during *in vitro* release studies. Carboxymethyl hexanoyl chitosan (CA)/GA cross linked Pluronic F127 hydrogel was prepared by Yap *et al.* for the loading of fibroblasts (L-929) [199]. The F127/CA/GA hydrogel was characterized for its thermal behaviour, swelling behaviour, the mechanical properties and alamar blue cell viability assay was performed to observe the viability of encapsulated cells. The hydrogel was stable in medium more than a month due to addition of CA and GA.

F127/CA/GA hydrogels were found to be non-cytotoxic in *in vitro* cell culture analysis. In another study, same research group prepared F127/CA/glyoxal (Gx) based thermoreversible injectable hydrogel for the encapsulation of human osteosarcoma MG-63 cells [200]. F127/CA/Gx hydrogel showed thermoreversible behaviour, thus, at room temperature it can liquify and back to gel state at body temperature. Furthermore, after 5-day incubation period, more than 400% proliferation of MG-63 cells was observed in this hydrogel. Fattahpour *et al.* synthesized and characterized CMCS/Pluronic/zinc chloride hydrogel system for encapsulating meloxicam loaded NPs [201]. The addition of NPs decreased the swelling time, gelation and the degradation rate of the hydrogels whereas an increase was observed with meloxicam solution. A complete release of meloxicam was observed from the meloxicam loaded hydrogel within 20 days, but a slow release (37 days) was noted from the NPs loaded hydrogels. Moreover, all the hydrogels found to increase the chondrocytes metabolic activity on the 6th and 10th days. Park and co-worker developed an injectable chitosan-Pluronic based cell delivery hydrogel by conjugating Pluronic onto chitosan using EDC/NHS chemistry [202]. The prepared hydrogel was characterized for rheological properties and morphological properties using different techniques. *In vitro* cell culture results evidenced an increase in chondrocyte proliferation and promoted extracellular matrix (ECM) molecules, thus can be used as an injectable cell delivery carrier for cartilage regeneration.

Copper NPs incorporated chitosan-Pluronic F127 (1:1) nanocomposite hydrogels were synthesized by Jayaramudu *et al.* [203]. Various techniques such as thermogravimetric analysis, SEM, TEM, FTIR and X-ray diffraction were employed for the characterization of prepared nanocomposite hydrogels. Moreover, nanocomposite hydrogels showed antimicrobial activity against both gram-negative (*E. coli*) and gram-positive (*S. aureus*) bacteria. Torabi *et al.* prepared an injectable melatonin-loaded chitosan-Pluronic hydrogel consisting GNPs and poly glycerol sebacate (PGS) for myocardial tissue engineering (field of

medical biotechnology to repair, regenerate or replace tissues or organs) MTT assay results showed an increase in cell viability with melatonin loaded hydrogel in H9C2 cells [204]. Chatterjee and co-worker developed and characterized a dual-responsive (pH/temperature) hydrogel consisted of N,N,N-trimethyl chitosan (TMC), polyethylene glycolated HA (PEG-HA) and Pluronic F127 [F127/TMC/PEG-HA]. Gallic acid was loaded into F127/TMC/PEG-HA hydrogel for its transdermal delivery in atopic dermatitis (AD) disease [205]. The prepared hydrogel was characterized using TEM, SEM, FTIR and zeta potential. The results indicated the better morphological and physicochemical properties of F127/TMC/PEG-HA hydrogel than for Pluronic F127 hydrogel. Dang and colleagues reported the CUR loaded Pluronic-chitosan hydrogel for the treatment of burn wounds [206]. These prepared formulations were characterized with wide range of techniques including UV-Vis, DLS, SEM and TEM; histopathological studies confirmed that fabricated hydrogel improved the repairing of burn wounds. Pham *et al.* fabricated a thermoresponsive hydrogel including Pluronic P123 and Chitosan as gelation component with CUR and gelatin as active ingredients for the tissue regeneration [207]. Furthermore, *in vitro* studies confirmed that the hydrogel enables the sustained release of CUR with excellent biocompatibility. Pluronic P123-grafted **chitosan-folate** nanogel system was developed for the codelivery of PTX and CUR by Nguyen and colleagues [208]. Gel system was characterized with bunch of techniques such as H-NMR, TGA, DLS, zeta potentials, and TEM. Enhanced anticancer activity against MCF-7 was observed with dual drug loaded nanogel system.

4.2 Pluronic-photo responsive hydrogels:

Development of Pluronic hydrogels with photo cleavable property has interesting applications in biomedicine as the drug load in the hydrogel can be released using light stimulus evidenced from various reports [209, 210]. Lee *et al.* developed photo crosslinked chitosan-Pluronic injectable hydrogels to enhance the transgene expression for gene therapy [211]. The

crosslinking of chitosan-Pluronic hydrogels to photo-irradiated hydrogels had done chemically at 37°C. By varying the mass erosion rates and photo-irradiation periods, release profiles of photo-crosslinked hydrogels were observed. The high amount of chitosan expedited the degradation rates of hydrogels while short photo-irradiation times led to the fast degradation of hydrogel. Yoon and co-worker [212] synthesized photo and thermo responsive hydrogels consisting Pluronic F127 and acrylic coumarin (AC) loaded with MB dye. Under UV irradiation, coumarin groups in hydrogels photo-dimerized and thus led to the suppressed release of MB dye (maximum at 23 and 50⁰ C) from hydrogels. The release of dye from the Pluronic F127/AC hydrogel can be altered by changing UV irradiation and temperature. Yoon *et al.* prepared photo-crosslinkable hydrogel consisted of di-acrylated Pluronic F127 and vinyl group conjugated heparin [213]. The prepared hydrogel composite was loaded with fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) to induce angiogenesis. Due to interaction of bFGF to heparin in the prepared hydrogel, a prolonged release of bFGF over a month was observed. *In vitro* study revealed that released bFGF showed appreciable proliferation activity of human umbilical vein endothelial cell (HUVEC) and moreover, implantation of prepared hydrogels showed a significant neovascularization *in vivo*. Lee *et al* synthesized a thermoresponsive and photo-crosslinkable hydrogel composed of HA and Pluronic F127 [214]. HA was pre-treated with aminopropyl methacrylamide (APMA) monomers to make it photo-cosslinkable. The prepared hydrogel was further conjugated with cell adhesive peptide (RGD) and loaded with bovine chondrocytes. Yoo and co-worker investigated photo-crosslinkable acrylated chitosan and Pluronic F127 based hydrogel for the release of human growth hormone (hGH) [215]. UV irradiation of gel above their gelation temperatures was employed for the preparation of photo-cross-linked chitosan/Pluronic F127 hydrogels. High chitosan content and long photo-cross-linking times led to the sustained release of hGH form the prepared hydrogels. Choi *et al.* developed a chitosan and di-acrylated Pluronic F127 based hydrogel encapsulated with a

recombinant human epidermal growth factor (rhEGF) to enhance wound healing [216]. The prepared hydrogel was photo-cross linked chemically and release of rhEGF from hydrogel was observed to be dependent on degradation rate. The chitosan-Pluronic hydrogel investigated *in vitro* as well *in vivo* for its wound healing properties and results showed a significant epidermal differentiation during the wound healing process. da Silva and colleagues prepared photo-responsive hydrogel system using Pluronic F127, Carbopol (C934P) and Safranin-O (Sf), act as photosensitizer [217]. The prepared hydrogels were characterized for their sol-gel transition temperature, mechanical as well as rheological properties, so that it can be used topically in veterinary (and human) applications.

4.3 Pluronic-Hyaluronic acid (HA) based hydrogels:

HA is a polysaccharide of natural origin and is present in many tissues, organs and its main abundance is in the human eye. HA made great progress in the drug delivery field due to its pronounced biocompatibility and biodegradability. To enhance the thermodynamic stability and to overcome the problems associated with Pluronic hydrogels, polysaccharides such as HA

Figure 16: (a) Sol-gel transition curves of Pluronic F-127 (●) and HA-Pluronic F127 (HP) hydrogel (○). (b) Photographs of the Piroxicam-loaded HP hydrogel obtained at 4 and 37.5 °C. Reprinted from Ref. 207; Jung *et al.*, Carbohydrate Polymers, 2016; 156: 403, Copyright (2016) Elsevier.

and alginates have used in conjugation with these gels. Especially, HA conjugation not only

increased the mechanical strength of Pluronic hydrogel but also promoted a sustained drug release [218]. In this section, we have discussed the modifying effect of HA while incorporating in Pluronic hydrogels. Jung *et al.* developed thermosensitive, HA and Pluronic F127 based an intra-articularly (IA) injectable hydrogel (HP) for the delivery of Piroxicam drug [219]. Synthesized hydrogels exhibited a lower critical gelation temperature (*CGT*) than pure Pluronic F127 hydrogels [Figure 16]. *In vitro* and *in vivo* results showed a sustained release of Piroxicam from Piroxicam-loaded HP hydrogel. Huh *et al.* designed a thermoresponsive hydrogel via crosslinking of methacrylate HA macromer with Pluronic P123 acrylate macromer [220]. HA/P123 hydrogels were characterized using SEM and results are shown in Figure 17. An ionic drug cefazoline and a non-ionic drug theophylline were loaded into each HA/P123 hydrogel and assessed for *in vitro* drug release. It was observed that upon

Figure 17: FE-SEM images (at different scale bar) showing (a) and (b) no foreign particles or formations on surface Pluronic P123 based HA hydrogel (HA/P123) and (c)-(f) formation of crystals within and on HA/P123 hydrogels after biomineralization process. Reprinted from Ref.208; Huh *et al.*, Carbohydrate Polymers, 2015;126: 130, Copyright (2015) Elsevier

increasing the water content of hydrogels accelerated drugs release was obtained. Authors emphasized that HA/P123 biomaterialized thermoresponsive injectable hydrogels can be used for bone tissue repair and regeneration purposes. Nascimento and co-worker prepared HA and Pluronic F127 and/or F108 hydrogels for the delivery of lidocaine drug [221]. Pluronic micellar interactions with HA have been studied using DLS and SAXS; sol to gel transitions were scrutinized with DSC and Rheology measurements. It has been observed that the addition of HA did not intervene with the thermoresponsive properties of the Pluronics but did effect on the morphological confirmations and drug release behaviour. *In vitro* release studies showed that increasing concentration of HA in hydrogel fasten the lidocaine release due to the morphological changes in hydrogels. Makvandi and colleagues synthesized wound healing hydrogels using microwave assisted green technique; main components of hydrogel system were consisted of Corn silk extract, HA, silver NPs (CSE/HA/Ag NPs), Pluronic F127 and F108 [222]. The prepared hydrogels showed good mechanical strength and body gelation temperature (T_{gel}) close to body temperature. The prepared hydrogels found to have anti-

Figure 18: Schematic illustration of injection of β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP)/CSE/HA/Ag NPs/Pluronic hydrogel for bone tissue regeneration. Reprinted from Ref. 211; Makvandi *et al.*, Materials Science and Engineering: C, 2020;107:110195, Copyright (2020) Elsevier.

bacterial properties against both gram positive and negative bacteria and showed expedited wound closure and repair in *in-vitro* model of wound healing as compared to the control. In another report, same research group prepared β -tricalcium

phosphate (β -TCP)/CSE/HA/Ag NPs/Pluronic F68 and F127 based thermosensitive hydrogels

for bone tissue regeneration application [223]. The prepared hydrogels also demonstrated anti-bacterial activity and promoted high bone differentiation of mesenchymal cells [Figure 18]. Rodriguez *et al.* developed a thermosensitive and IA Pluronic F127/P123/HA based injectable hydrogel for the loading of beta-lapachone for its use in osteoarthritis (OA) management [224]. These hydrogels showed temperature dependent rheological properties; at 25 °C viscosity of hydrogel was controlled by the HA concentration, on the other hand, at 37 °C it was managed by Pluronic F127/P123. *ex vivo* OA model was developed to evaluate the therapeutic potential of prepared hydrogel. Moreover, a marked decrease in the release of degradative and pro-inflammatory markers was observed with these hydrogels and can be employed in the OA management. Secer and colleagues prepared an injectable thermoresponsive hydrogel comprising of HA and Pluronic F127 [225]. Concentration range of HA from 1.6 to 2% w/v promote the gelation of mixed hydrogel system of Pluronic F127/HA while upon increasing the concentration > 2% w/v decrease the gelation temperature to room temperature. So, concentration of HA was fixed at 2% w/v for F127/HA hydrogel system and further studied the addition of α , β - and γ -Cyclodextrin (CD). Pluronic F127/HA/ α , β - and γ -CD hydrogel showed the injectable and mucoadhesive properties which can be used for therapeutic delivery in ear surgery. Rosuvastatin (RSV) loaded chitosan/chondroitin sulfate NPs were incorporated in to thermosensitive Pluronic F127/HA hydrogels by Rezazadeh and co-worker [226]. *In vitro* cell cultures evidenced that RSV loaded hydrogels was able to maintain the osteoblast viability and proliferation and can be used as delivery carrier for RSV in bone tissue engineering. A thermosensitive injectable Pluronic F127/HA hydrogel was developed by Hsieh *et al.* to encapsulate urokinase for its use in bone regeneration [227]. The Pluronic/HA hydrogel was characterized for micellization, gel dissolution and gel microstructure using different techniques. *In vitro* drug release study showed the prolonged and sustained release of Urokinase from the prepared hydrogel. Chen *et al.* investigated an injectable Pluronic

F127/HA/ poly (γ -glutamic acid) (PGA) hydrogel for the loading of monoclonal antibody drug infliximab (IFX) [228]. IFX loaded Pluronic F127/HA/PGA hydrogel demonstrated sustained drug release and appreciable biocompatibility and biodegradability. The prepared hydrogels abrogated the release of various pro-inflammatory cytokines, relieved pain and prevented cartilage destruction in Rheumatoid arthritis (RA). A thermosensitive injectable DOX loaded Pluronic F127/HA hydrogel was developed by Jhan *et al.* for cancer treatment [229]. *In vitro* cell line study revealed that DOX loaded hydrogel inhibited the growth of C26 colon cancer cells. Moreover, *in vivo* study was conducted using a tumour xenograft mouse model and the lymphatic system targeting was observed using HA. Jung *et al.* developed Pluronic F127/HA hydrogels for the delivery of transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1) [230]. The prepared hydrogel exhibited effective induction of chondrogenic differentiation of human adipose-derived stem cells (ASCs).

4.4 Pluronic-gelatin based hydrogels:

Gelatin is a natural polymer (protein) and denatured product of collagen extracted from skin, bones, and connective tissues of animals. Gelatin has appreciable biodegradability, biocompatibility and nonimmunogenicity. Around human body temperature, gelatin hydrogels are in the liquid form and upon cooling, exists as thermo-reversible gels. However, the weak elasticity, poor mechanical strength and low shape stability are the main disadvantages of gelatin hydrogels that limit their biomedical applications. To overcome this problem, numerous strategies have been used such as addition of chemical crosslinker to gelatin. Pluronic has been used in conjunction with gelatin to reduce its associated problems [231-234]. Moreover, the addition of gelatin to Pluronic hydrogels increase the loading capacity of Pluronic hydrogels. In line with this, Tatini *et al.* investigated the synthesis and release behaviour of Pluronic F127 and gelatin based hydrogel that can be used for the drugs or nutrients administration [235]. A simple injection method was employed for the preparation of these

hydrogels in which cold solution of Pluronic F127 was injected into hot gelatin solution. UV/Vis spectrophotometry was employed to observe azorubine release from prepared hydrogels (PGC) along with effect of temperature and pH on the release mechanism [Figure 19]. Temperature and pH dependent release profiles were obtained, and more sustained release was observed at 37°C. The combination of Pluronic F127 and gelatin overcome the limitation associated with each other

Figure 19: (a) UV/Vis absorption spectra of Azorubine and Gelatin at different pH (2 and 7) at 37 °C , (b) Illustration of the azorubine release from PGCs experiment. (c) UV/Vis absorption spectra of PGCs (at 25 °C) at different pH values with increasing time. Reprinted from Ref. 223; Tatini *et al.*, Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerface, 2015;135: 400, Copyright (2015), with permission from Elsevier.

and thus, make them suitable carrier for enteral administration. A reverse thermoresponsive, Pluronic F127 and gelatin based hydrogel was prepared by Yeh and co-worker [236]. By varying the amount and type of gelatin [Type A (GA) and type B (GB)], the stiffness of Pluronic F127-gelatin hydrogel can be modified. Rheological data results evidenced that the gel strength of PF127-GA found to be higher as compared to the PF127-GB gels. Furthermore,

in vitro study on human MSC cells showed the significant biocompatibility and cell viability with the use of Pluronic F127-gelatin hydrogel. Pan and co-worker using two different materials for skin tissue engineering applications fabricated a bilayer scaffold [237].

The upper layer biomaterial was a Poly(ϵ -caprolactone-co-lactide)/Pluronic (PLCL/ Pluronic) and the lower layer consisted of 10% dextran and 20% gelatin hydrogel. PLCL/Pluronic

Figure 20. SEM images of electrospun PLCL/Pluronic hydrogel with different weight ratio of PLCL to Pluronic: (a) 1/0; (b) 9/1; (c) 3/1. Reprinted from Ref. 225; Pan *et al.*, PLoS One, 2014;9: e112885. Copyright (2014) PLOS.

hydrogel was characterized using various *in vitro* techniques [SEM images shown in **Figure 20**]. The upper layer membrane provided mechanical support in the scaffold while the lower layer hydrogel offered the appropriate space for cell proliferation and generation of extracellular matrix. The prepared bilayer scaffold showed good mechanical strength and biocompatibility in *in vitro* studies. A thermosensitive Pluronic grafted gelatin (PG) and nanocurcumin (nCur) based hydrogel was designed to enhance burn healing [238]. DLS and TEM results showed the 1.5 ± 0.5 to 16 ± 3.2 nm size distribution of the dispersed nCur. A sustained release of Cur was observed from the prepared nanocomposite hydrogel. Histology results evidenced that PG-Cur hydrogel significantly enhanced the healing process of second-degree burn created on animal skin. The study on fibroblast cells indicated the biocompatibility of nCur-PG hydrogel and found to increase the proliferation of cells as well. Nguyen and colleagues prepared nanogel composed of gelatin conjugated with Pluronic (F127, F87) to increase the efficacy and delivery of nCUR [239]. nCUR loaded nanogel was highly stable and showed significantly higher cytotoxicity in cancer cells as compared to free CUR. Same research group in other report, investigated hydrogel by grafting gelatin with Pluronic P123, F127, F87 and F68 and used for the delivery of QCT [240]. The change in the cytotoxic effect has been observed by tuning the lipophilicity (using different Pluronic) of Pluronic-gelatin hydrogels on HeLa and MCF-7 cancer cell lines.

Pluronic-functionalized platforms for cell delivery

Table 3: Hydrogels comprising Pluronic-Chitosan/Gelatin/HA and Photo cross linked moieties for loading of various therapeutics.

Functionalization	Payload	Pluronic	Targeted disease and cell lines
Chitosan based hydrogel (CMCS, CA, TMC)	PTX, NP, NO, 5-FU, L-929, Meloxicam, Copper NPs,	F127	Hepatoma solidity cell (Heps) tumour-bearing mice (anti-cancer activity), Human corneal epithelial cells, Activity against <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , Anti-microbial activity, human osteosarcoma MG-63 cells,

	Melatonin, Gallic acid		H2C9 cells (myocardial tissue engineering) [195-208]
Photo cross-linked hydrogel	MB, bFGF, Bovine chondrocytes, hGH, rhEGF	F127, di-acrylated Pluronic F127	Human umbilical vein endothelial cell (HUVEC), wound healing activity (<i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i>) [211-217]
Hyaluronic acid (HA) cross-linked hydrogel	Piroxicam, Cefazoline, Theophylline, Lidocaine, β -TCP, β -lapachone, RSV, Urokinase, IFX, DOX, TGF- β 1	F127, P123, F108, F68	Anti-bacterial activity, <i>in-vitro</i> wound healing activity, mesenchymal cells (bone tissue regeneration application), <i>ex vivo</i> osteoarthritis (OA) activity, bone tissue engineering, C26 cells (colon cancer), <i>in vivo</i> activity in tumour xenograft mouse model, human adipose-derived stem cells (ASCs) [219-230]
Gelatin cross-linked hydrogels	CUR, QCT	P123, F127, F87, F68	Hela, MCF-7 [235-240]

5.0 Pluronics as stabilizer for the formation of different nano-formulations

The stability of NPs, cubosomes and nanocrystals depend upon many factors such as solubility, hydrophobicity, surface energy, viscosity and functional groups.; Pluronics are being exploited to stabilize these systems. Numerous literatures reports showed the formation of a stable thermodynamic and mechanical barrier with the addition of Pluronic to NPs that prevent the aggregation of particles and provide the stability to the formulation [241-244]. Gandhi and colleagues stabilized the Eudragit RLPO (cationic polymer dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate) NPs with Pluronic F68 for sustained delivery of antiviral drug Acyclovir [241]. FA conjugated Eudragit S-100 based NPs were explored to effectively target the over expressed folate receptors in colon cancer in which Pluronic F68 have been used as stabilizer [242]. In another report, Pluronic F68 was been used to provide the stable mechanical strength to solid lipid NPs used for the antibacterial activity of clarithromycin [243]. Pluronic F68 was used also to stabilize the PLGA NPs for the targeted delivery of brain [244, 245]. Lale *et al.* evidenced that

Pluronic F68 prevented the aggregation and provide the stabilization to pH responsive poly(dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate)-poly(polyethylene glycol methacrylate)-poly(caprolactone)-poly(polyethylene glycol methacrylate)-poly(dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate) NPs and designed to improve the DOX efficacy in breast cancer therapy [246]. SN38 conjugated tocopherol succinate NPs were stabilized using Pluronic F68 for their delivery to Neuroblastoma (NB) tumour in mice. The prepared NPs showed better efficacy, stability, and enhanced retention time in NB tumour [247]. Guven *et al.* used Pluronic F108 to stabilize an ultrashort single-walled carbon nanocapsules for the chemotherapeutic delivery of Cisplatin [248] and dual delivery of DTX and interference peptides was achieved using poly(acrylic acid) functionalized poly(glycidyl methacrylate) NPs that were stabilized with Pluronic F108 [249]. Zhai and co-worker exploited Pluronic F127 as a stabilizer for lipid NPs which were further explored for the target ability to EGFR overexpressed cancer cells [250]. Kapoor *et al.* explored the intracellular delivery of peptide using polyhydroxybutyrate based NPs stabilized with Pluronic F127 [251]. Pluronic-grafted chitosan was synthesized by Sharma and colleagues and used as stabilizers for PTX encapsulated nanocrystals preparation [252]. Pluronic F127 used as stabilizer for lutein loaded in zein NPs and monoolein-capric acid NPs [253, 254] and Pluronic F127, P123 had been used to stabilize the gelatin nanocomposite for the delivery of CUR [255]. Ondansetron loaded Pluronic F127 stabilized reduced graphene oxide hydrogel as a promising transdermal delivery system on the other hand Pluronic F127 stabilized reduced graphene oxide hydrogel used for psoriasis treatment and sustained delivery of ketamine through transdermal route [256-258]. TiO₂ NPs were stabilized with Pluronic L35 and F68 to improve the distribution of NPs in a hydrogel [259]. Solid lipid NPs laden contact lens was stabilized using and employed for the delivery of epalrestat to the eyes [260]. Transdermal hydrogel formulation was prepared using graphene oxide (GO) stabilized by Pluronic F68 for the delivery of flurbiprofen [261]. Nano-cubosomal formulation prepared

using glyceryl monooleate, Cremophor EL stabilized by Pluronic F108 or Pluronic F127 was used to deliver Norfloxacin for otitis externa [262]. Cubosomes stabilized by a poly(phosphoester) (PPE) analogue of Pluronic F127 were prepared and cytotoxicity study in HEK-293, HUVEC and human red blood cells evidenced significantly less toxicity as compared to cubosomes prepared using Pluronic F127 [263]. On the other hand, Lee and colleagues exploited the Polyvinylpyrrolidone and Pluronic F127 to produce polymer composite accommodating anti-inflammatory drug Celecoxib. Prepared nanocomposites showed the improved bioavailability and Polyvinylpyrrolidone composite also exhibited improved *in vitro* Celecoxib release [264]. Gaggero *et al.* adopted a co-grinding approach using surfactants *viz.* Pluronic F127 and sucrose stearate to improve physicochemical and biopharmaceutical properties of poorly soluble drug Praziquantel. The obtained formulations with co-grinding approach embarked the improved *in vitro* dissolution properties as well as *in vitro* permeability tested in Caco-2 cells [265].

6.0 Pluronic based Emulsions:

Emulsions are basically known as colloidal systems in which droplets of one liquid is dispersed in another immiscible liquid with the help of a surfactants. Micro and nano-emulsions have attracted particular interest as promising drug-delivery nanocarriers because can solubilize the poor soluble drugs, encapsulation protects the drugs from degradation and moreover, are biocompatible. Although wide range of immense properties, the main issue is their stability and therefore the selection of appropriate surfactant and co-surfactant is critical. The non-ionic Pluronics (Poloxamers) are well known for their stabilization and bio-compatible properties and provide better colloidal stability to microemulsions as compared to other classical surfactants [266-270]. Rahdar and co-worker developed oil-in-water Pluronic F127-based microemulsions for the loading of MTX [271]. The Pluronic-microemulsion showed high encapsulation capacity and further MTX loaded and unformulated MTX was observed for its

toxicity in a Wistar rat model. The effect of Pluronic P123 and phospholipid [1,2-Dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC), 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE)] on emulsifying capacity and stability was investigated by Yang *et al* [272]. *In-vitro* study results evidenced the formation of smaller, more uniform and stable droplets with the use of DOPC, DOPE, and Pluronic P123 mixed emulsifier-stabilized emulsions. Wik and colleagues prepared nanoemulsions using hydrophobic poly(δ -decalactone) (PDL) as oil and Pluronic F68 as surfactant to increase the solubility of five different hydrophobic drugs (carvedilol, CUR, cyclosporine A, griseofulvin, and prednisolone) [273]. The solubility of drugs was enhanced by 3-10 times and cytotoxicity study of CUR loaded nanoemulsion exhibited time-concentration dependent toxicity in MDA-MB-231 cell line. An oil-in-water nanoemulsion based thermogelling system was synthesized through a low-energy method by Hashemnejad *et al*. Pluronic mixture (F127/F68: 6/1 g/g) was used as gelling agent in nanoemulsions

Figure 21: Schematic representation of the synthesis of enzyme-Pluronic nanoconjugates and microgels via reverse emulsions. Reprinted from Ref. 261; Wu *et al.*, Chemical Communications, 2015;51: 9674, Copyright (2015) Royal Society of Chemistry.

preparation [274]. The authors suggested that thermoresponsive nanoemulsion gel can potentially be used as drug carrier for transdermal and topical formulation. Wu and co-worker synthesized enzyme-Pluronic nanoconjugates in reverse emulsion using aldehyde-functionalized Pluronic F127 as a reactive surfactant [275]. The reverse emulsion formed by this reactive surfactant showed promise

for encapsulating enzymes without enzyme deactivation [Figure 21]. Quintana *et al.* developed

w/o emulsions using Pluronic, acrylic acid and okara oil in microfluidic devices to encapsulate probiotic *Lactobacillus plantarum* CIDCA 83114 [276]. The prepared emulsion protected the probiotic from gastric environment and no significant changes were observed. Self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS) was developed for the targeted specific delivery of ciprofloxacin (CIP) to intracellular *Salmonella typhi* bacterium [277]. SEDDS were prepared using Oleic oil (oil), Tween 80 (surfactant), PEG 200 (co-surfactant) and Pluronic F127 and poly-L-lysine functionalized carbohydrates were used to augment the mucopenetration of SEDDS. The prepared SEDDS of CIP exhibited excellent killing of *Salmonella typhi* strains at very low concentration as compared to CIP alone.

7.0 Miscellaneous

Due to appreciable properties of Pluronics, they can be further functionalized with other moieties such as antibodies, aptamers, nanosheets and functionalized with heparin to prepare injectable hydrogels. Antibody has specific ability to target cell of interest such as cancer cells, brain cells etc. combining the advantages of antibody, Song *et al.* targeted the stomach cancer cells using anti-HIF-1 α antibody conjugated PTX loaded Pluronic P123 micelles [278]. The prepared nanocomposites showed remarkable cytotoxicity to MGC-803 stomach cancer cells and did not affect the normal cells. In another report, Gan and colleagues used anti-GPC3 antibody functionalized Pluronic NPs for specific delivery of sorafenib in HepG2 human liver cells [279]. To target MCF-7/ADR breast cancer cells, CD44 antibody have been introduced to dendrimer conjugated Pluronic P123 for anti-MDR1 shRNA-encoding plasmid DNA delivery depicted in **Figure 22** [280]. Andrade *et al.* prepared niclosamide (NCS) loaded Pluronic F127 micelles functionalized with an antibody CD44v6 for colorectal cancer stem cells (CSC) [281]. Functionalization of antibody resulted in the enhanced internalization of NCS loaded micelles in CD44v6+ cells. *In vivo* study evidenced the decrease in circulating tumour cells (CTC) with the administration of functionalized micelles.

Aptamers are single-stranded RNA or DNA ligands that can bind to the target site with high specificity and affinity. Owing to their unique characteristics such as low toxicity, small size, stability, fast and cheaper preparation processing, make them attractive to use for the targeted delivery of payloads [282,283]. In line with this, DOX delivery to breast cancer cells was observed using surface modified aptamer AS1411 with Pluronic F127 and beta-cyclodextrin-linked poly(ethylene glycol)-b-poly lactide [284]. *In vivo* activity of aptamer functionalized Pluronic in tumour bearing mice showed the enhanced accumulation of DOX in tumour cells, high retention time and enhanced anti-cancer activity. Nguyen *et al.* developed aptamer modified Pluronic F127/chitosan micelles for PTX delivery to HER-2 overexpressing

Figure 22: Schematic representation of the gene-silencing system of anti-CD44-P123-PPI/pDNA-iMDR1-shRNA nanocomplexes to deliver anti-MDR1 shRNA-encoding plasmid DNA to human breast cancer cells for overcoming drug resistance and enhancing chemotherapy efficacy. Reprinted from Ref. 266; Biomaterials, 2015;45: 99, Copyright (2015) Elsevier.

SK-BR-3 human breast cancer cells [285]. High loading capacity ($9.12 \pm 0.34\%$) and encapsulation efficiency ($83.28 \pm 0.13\%$) was observed with PTX loaded aptamer modified Pluronic F127/chitosan micelles. Moreover, MTT assay results evidenced the higher *in vitro* cytotoxicity of prepared micelles as compared to PTX alone. Same research group in their other report observed the anti-cancer effect of PTX loaded aptamer modified Pluronic F127/chitosan

micelles in cancer cell lines [286]. The prepared micelles exhibited higher cytotoxicity in NS-VN-67, LH-VN-48, HT-VN-26 and NV-VN-31 cancer cell lines. Recently, Chen *et al.* used Pluronic F127 to coat the surface of molybdenum oxide (MoO_x) nanosheets for the delivery of DOX drug and chemo-photothermal combination cancer therapy [287]. Murine breast cancer 4T1 cells and MCF-7 human breast cancer cells were treated with Pluronic coated nanosheets for DOX induced chemotherapy. Therefore, there is huge scope of Pluronics to coat a hydrophobic surface of inorganic nanomaterial to improve their biocompatibility and drug loading capacity. However, there are limited research on inorganic nanosheet functionalization with Pluronics, more research is required for drug delivery applications.

Heparin, a highly negatively charged glycosaminoglycan, is also explored with Pluronics to prepare hydrogels. Choi and co-worker reported the delivery of RNAase to HeLa Cells using heparin functionalized Pluronic F127 hydrogels [288]. Same research group used this hydrogel system for the co-delivery of PTX and DNase to the intracellular sites of a cancer cell [289]. Temperature-sensitive and biocompatible injectable hydrogel have been synthesized using heparin-functionalized Pluronic F127 and DOX conjugated Laponite RDS nanosilicate for efficient tumour therapy [290].

Other most extensively studied class of drug carriers is Liposomes, typically liposomes comprised of phospholipids and cholesterol bilayers. Hydrophobic drugs are mostly loaded in the hydrophobic part of liposome bilayer whereas hydrophilic drug preferably solubilized in inner aqueous part. Liposomes are coated with Pluronics to improve their stability and mucoadhesive properties. In this regards, Chen and co-worker did a comparative study using Chitosan and Pluronic F127 coated liposomes on the mucus penetration of hydrophobic drug Cyclosporin in rats. Stability of the different micelles depicted in **Figure 23**. Authors observed that Pluronic F127 coated liposomes having a better Gastro-intestinal (GI) stability and penetration in the mucus layers to reach the epithelial surface as compared to Chitosan coated

Liposomes [291]. Li *et al.* reported a Pluronic F127 coated liposomes loaded with Coumarin-6, cellular uptake of these liposomes analysed on Caco-2 cells [292].

Figure 23: Stability of liposomes in simulated gastrointestinal fluids. (a) Particle size of Liposomes (Lip), PF127-Lip and Chitosan (CS)-Lip incubated for 2 h in SGF (pH 1.2); (b) particle size of Lip, PF127-Lip and CS-Lip incubated in SIF for 6 h (pH 6.8); (c) photographic images of liposomes upon adding SIF; (d) photographic images of liposomes incubated in SIF for 6 h (large particle aggregates formed as indicated with red circle). Reprinted from Ref. 277; Chen *et al.*, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2013; 449: 1, Copyright (2013) Elsevier.

Zhu and colleagues explored the improvement of solubility and intestinal penetration of tacrolimus in the GI tract using Pluronic modified liposomes inclusion with cyclodextrin [293]. Wang and co-worker reported the Pluronic L61 functionalized liposomes for PTX delivery. PTX loaded liposomes showed long-circulating activity and preferentially accumulated in the tumour site [294]. Li *et. al* assessed different Pluronics F127, F87 and P85 coated on CUM loaded liposomes to improve the stability and bioaccessibility [295]. Pluronic F127 modified CUR loaded liposomes embarked best GI tract absorption than other Pluronic modified CUR

loaded liposomes. Pluronic L64 modified liposomes loaded with RES drug with enhanced stability, biocompatibility and antioxidant activity was observed by Caddeo and colleagues [296].

Figure 24: Schematic representation of cinnamoyl (CP)-Pluronic F127 liposomes for dual responsiveness against Light and temperature. Reprinted from Ref. 283; Wang *et al.*, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2014; 468:243-9, Copyright (2014), Elsevier.

Wang and colleagues reported an interesting study in which they used cinnamoyl Pluronic F127 (CP F127) decorated liposomes for dual responsiveness against Light and temperature [297]. Upon UV irradiation to these prepared liposomes, photodimerization of cinnamoyl moieties perturbs the liposomal membrane results in the release of a fluorescent dye calcein. Furthermore, on higher temperature due to dehydration of Pluronic F127 layer on the liposomal surface results in phase transition and released of calcein (**Figure 24**). Synthetic Toll-like receptor-4 agonist and CRX-601 carrying liposomes were modified with Pluronic, PEG and chitosan and investigated in a SL murine influenza vaccine model to produce an immune response. Modified

liposomes showed the improved flu-specific immune response as compared to unmodified liposomes [298]. Lee and colleagues fabricated an injectable hydrogel consist of adamantane conjugated Pluronic F127 and β -cyclodextrin, for the delivery of Insulin a protein. Authors expected this injectable formulation can be useful for versatile protein delivery system with controllable drug release properties [299]. However, there are limited studies in which Pluronics have been functionalized with different moieties for the cell delivery for wider applications such as tissue regeneration. Volkmer *et al.* extended the Pluronic P123 structure with different hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI), butane diisocyanate (BDI) and hydrogenated diphenylmethane diisocyanate chains as cell-based hydrogel system [300]. Dang and colleagues fabricated a hydrogel system using sodium alginate and Pluronic F127 for the tissue regeneration applications [310]. Prepared hydrogels have antibacterial activity due to CYS linker in hydrogel as well as cyto-compatible with fibroblast cells. Authors declared that these type of modified Pluronic hydrogels have a wider scope in the cellular delivery systems.

8.0 Conclusion and future aspects:

The past 15 years have evidenced an expeditious development of functionalized Pluronics in the area of drug delivery. Despite this fact, Pluronic's commercial availability as well as non-ionic properties, biocompatibility and biodegradability make them attractive for therapeutics delivery and applications. Pluronics are extensively functionalized to enable their target ability to specific cells and stimuli responsive using activation of the terminal hydroxyl group. Moreover, to improve their drug loading capacity, Pluronics are directly conjugated with drug molecules. Publications cited in this review demonstrated that NPs conjugation with Pluronics is a useful method for drug delivery as Pluronics improve NPs dispersity, biocompatibility, and drug loading capacity. In addition, conjugation with NPs improved the overall stability of Pluronics. Hydrogels are reported for injectable delivery of anticancer drugs and some are

related to wound healing and anti-microbial properties. There is also scope for the use of functionalized Pluronic hydrogels in topical drug delivery such as ear, vaginal, rectal and ocular. Furthermore, inorganic nanomaterials such as made-up molybdenum can be coated with Pluronics for suitable drug delivery applications as they have hydrophobic surfaces which can be modulated using Pluronics. Thus, we have summarized Pluronics and their functionalization for applications as therapeutic delivery vehicles and therefore, functionalized Pluronics can be envisioned as suitable drug carriers in upcoming years.

Although functionalized Pluronics have rapidly emerged in the field of therapeutics delivery, most publications focus on cancer treatment using different cancer cell lines. Consequently, there is significant potential for utilizing functionalized Pluronics in targeting specific organs and preventing the degradation of drugs. Considering this, in near the future, functionalized Pluronics can be assumed to use for the delivery of various drugs to other organs of the human body. Although research on antibody and aptamer functionalized Pluronics is still in its infancy, there is a pressing need for these materials for drug delivery, alongside biosensing applications. With functionalization of Pluronics with different ligands, new hydrogels will be produced using other emerging techniques such as 3D and 4D bioprinting, as well as *in vivo* bioprinting for tissue engineering applications in the near future. However, functionalized Pluronics face many hurdles as delivery vehicles due to numerous intracellular and extracellular barriers. Moreover, the limited animal model studies and their limitations in terms of toleration and whether they are non-toxic on repeated administration are a major concern. Intensive and systematic research on functionalized Pluronics with a range of experts such as formulation scientists, clinicians, oncologists, and doctors would be fruitful for real-time applications in nanomedicine, as well as other clinical and theranostics purposes.

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